

NFDI4Energy –
National Research Data
Infrastructure for
Interdisciplinary Energy
System Research
Progress Report

NFDI4Energy – National Research Data Infrastructure for Inter- disciplinary Energy System Research: Progress Report

Astrid Nieße^{1,2}, Stephan Ferenz^{1,2}, Sören Auer³, Felix Engel³, Olha Finke², Jan Forberg⁴,
Laura Fuentes Grau⁵, Reinhard German⁶, Veit Hagenmeyer⁷, Franziska Hoffart⁸, Jonas Huber⁹,
Ludwig Hülk⁹, Oliver Karras³, Florian Kotthoff², Lea Kuhlmann², Sebastian Lehnhoff^{1,2},
Johan Lilliestam¹⁰, Antonello Monti⁵, Laura Niemann², Allard Oelen³, Zhiyu Pan⁵,
Mascha Richter⁹, Philipp Rohde³, Mirko Schäfer¹¹, Philipp Schmurr⁷, Jan Sören Schwarz^{1,2},
Corinna Seiwerth⁶, Michael Selzer¹², Christina Speck¹³, Mirjam Stappel¹⁴, Alexandro Steinert^{1,2},
Wolfgang Süß⁷, Berthold Vogel⁸, Anke Weidlich¹¹, Amanda Wein^{1,2}, Christof Weinhardt¹³,
Oliver Werth²

¹ Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Department of Computer Science,
Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118, 26129 Oldenburg

² OFFIS – Institute for Information Technology, Energy Division, Escherweg 2, 26121 Oldenburg

³ TIB Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Welfengarten 1B,
30167 Hannover

⁴ Institut für Angewandte Informatik (InfAI) e.V., Goedelerring 9, 04109 Leipzig

⁵ RWTH Aachen, Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, Mathieustraße 10,
52074 Aachen

⁶ Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Chair of Computer Science 7 (Computer
Networks and Communication Systems), Martensstraße 3, 91058 Erlangen

⁷ Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Institute for Automation and Applied Informatics,
Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen

⁸ Sociological Research Institute Göttingen e.V. (SOFI), Friedländer Weg 31, 37085 Göttingen

⁹ Reiner Lemoine Institut (RLI), Rudower Chaussee 12, 12489 Berlin

¹⁰ Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Chair of Sustainability Transition Policy,
Lange Gasse 20, 90403 Nürnberg

¹¹ University of Freiburg, INATECH, Emmy-Noether-Str. 2, 79110 Freiburg im Breisgau

¹² Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Institute of Nanotechnology, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-
Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen

¹³ Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Institute for Information Systems, Kaiserstraße 93,
76133 Karlsruhe

¹⁴ Osnabrück University, Institute of Computer Science, Neuer Graben 29 / Schloss,
49074 Osnabrück

Published by

Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg

Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118

26129 Oldenburg

Acknowledgements

The authors of this report have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named.

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

License

This document is published under the [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). This license allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use.

Contents

Part B1	4
1 General Information	4
2 Summary	5
3 Composition of the consortium	7
Part B2	9
1 Consortium	9
1.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest	10
1.2 The consortium within the NFDI / General Contribution to the development of the NFDI	12
1.3 International networking	15
1.4 Organizational structure and viability / sustainability	16
1.5 Operating model	17
2 Research Data Management Strategy	18
2.1 Scientific relevance and quality of the measures	19
2.2 Metadata standards and reliable services	20
2.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance	23
2.4 Services provided by the consortium	24
2.5 Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints	29
3 Additional Aspects	30
3.1 Equal opportunities	30
3.2 Reflections and comments	31
Appendix	33
1 List of outputs produced by the consortium	33
1.1 Abstracts	33
1.2 Book chapters	35
1.3 Conference posters	36
1.4 Conference proceedings	37
1.5 Deliverables	38
1.6 Journal articles	40
1.7 Presentations	41
1.8 Other	43
2 Bibliography	43
3 List of Acronyms	50

Part B1

1 General Information

- Name of the consortium
NFDI4Energy – National Research Data Infrastructure for the Interdisciplinary Energy System Research

- Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium

Classification according to DFG review boards:

- 1.23 Social Sciences
- 1.24 Economics
- 4.41 Systems Engineering
- 4.42 Electrical Engineering and Information Technology
- 4.43 Computer Science

As NFDI4Energy, we address interdisciplinary energy system research, which includes technical, social, economic, policy, and socio-technical aspects of the transformation of energy systems. This transformation creates complex research challenges due to strong interconnections between power, heat, mobility, and increasing digitalization. We aim to support reproducible research in energy system modeling, simulation, and analysis by providing community services for managing digital objects such as models, datasets, workflows and scenarios across scales.

- URL of the consortium website and repositories used for publishing output

Website	https://nfdi4energy.uol.de/
Zenodo community for outputs	https://zenodo.org/communities/nfdi4energy/
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4energy/

2 Summary

As NFDI4Energy, we aim to make data and software the scientific foundation for a sustainable energy future. Good research data management (RDM) in energy system research is key for the **interdisciplinary collaboration** that is essential to tackle the technical, social, economic, policy, and socio-technical dimensions of the energy transition. By ensuring that research outputs are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), RDM will simplify the use of artificial intelligence, shorten innovation cycles, reduce duplications, foster excellent research, and drive the scientific advances needed for a sustainable energy future.

We have positioned NFDI4Energy as the **central hub for RDM in the energy domain**. Halfway through its first funding phase, NFDI4Energy in the NFDI association grew from its 10 original members to 26 members through our active community engagement. We conduct **yearly NFDI4Energy Conferences**, which bring together researchers, industry partners, public administrative bodies, and societal actors. More than half of the conference participants came from non-funded organizations, thus showing the success of our community work. In addition, through further community work (for example, by booths and keynotes at conferences), we foster the cultural change towards FAIR data in energy system research. Our work in NFDI4Energy is guided by our professional scientific and industrial advisory boards.

Concrete showcases have proven to be an effective way to turn RDM concepts and services into success stories and to communicate them throughout the community. For example, one showcase illustrates how FAIR climate policy datasets based on ontology-driven workflows can support quantitative policy effectiveness analyses, e.g., for the upcoming assessment of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

Our **NFDI4Energy service portfolio** integrates services developed by different initiatives. Thereby, it forms the backbone of good RDM in energy system research. By evaluating and adapting these solutions, we built a coherent service portfolio that leverages proven methods while also filling identified RDM gaps. The portfolio is based on a clear sustainable onboarding process to ensure the quality of the services. These services span the entire data lifecycle as follows: the **Terminology Service** offers searchable access to energy ontologies; **RDMO4Energy** provides energy-specific data management plan templates; the **Open Energy Scenario Bundles** allow users to document scenario context and to link studies, models, and data through a knowledge graph; the **Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)** enables semantic description and comparison of publications enhanced with energy-specific ontologies; the **Leibniz Data Manager (LDM)** federates data upload, data linking with natural language queries, and data exploration; the **Open Energy Database** provides a data repository using a community-driven metadata schema; and the **Open Energy Databus** links heterogeneous data across lifecycles

via a metadata knowledge graph. The services will be further enhanced in the second part of this funding phase based on community feedback. Through additional showcases, we will illustrate the benefits of the services to our community and further increase their usage.

An energy-specific **metadata schema** and energy-specific **ontologies** are essential to unlock the full potential of these services and the datasets. For example, better dataset descriptions help to enable the usage of datasets in artificial-intelligence based systems. Therefore, we adopted the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) as the primary domain ontology and contributed new concepts on topics such as long-term scenario modeling. We also established a metadata schema for energy data and synchronized it with the activities in the other NFDI consortia.

Research software is a key research artifact in the energy domain. Recognizing that energy system research benefits from **research software engineering (RSE)**, we started an energy research software engineering community. We introduced a metadata schema for energy research software and incorporated software management plan templates into RDMO4Energy. With this work, we contributed to a better connection between the RSE and RDM communities.

As NFDI4Energy, we foster the **idea of oneNFDI**, e.g., by integrating different **base services** like IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI, and DMP4NFDI. We contribute to oneNFDI through our support of new service initiatives like nfdi.software, as well as through our active participation in the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI, 2023 & 2025), the NFDI sections, and the NFDI task forces, e.g., on Governance and Sustainability. We collaborate with other NFDI consortia and regularly invite them to our NFDI4Energy Conferences, including active roles, e.g., with keynotes, booths, and workshops. Our collaboration with other NFDI consortia also includes the establishment of Memorandums of Understandings and the preparation of joint calls for **flex projects**.

Through our community work, we have identified additional needs for domain-specific RDM training, which we will address in the next funding phase. There is an increasing demand for reusable, quality-assured, annotated data from academia, public administration, and industry, which we will further concentrate on.

In summary, NFDI4Energy has become **the central hub for RDM in the energy domain**, delivering a dedicated suite of quality-assured services, developing energy-specific metadata and ontologies, integrating existing approaches, and providing showcases as a basis for our successful community work.

3 Composition of the consortium

- Applicant institution

Applicant institution	Location	Duration
Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg (UOL)	Oldenburg	02/2023 -

- Spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location	Duration
Prof. Dr. Astrid Nieße 0000-0003-1881-9172	UOL, Oldenburg	02/2023 -

- Co-applicant institutions

Co-applicant institutions	Location	Duration
Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg (UFR)	Freiburg	02/2023 -
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)	Erlangen-Nürnberg	02/2023 -
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)	Karlsruhe	02/2023 -
OFFIS e.V.	Oldenburg	02/2023 -
RWTH Aachen	Aachen	02/2023 -
Soziologisches Forschungsinstitut Göttingen (SOFI) e.V.	Göttingen	02/2023 -
Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB)	Hannover	02/2023 -

- Co-spokespersons

Co-spokespersons	Institution, location	Task area(s)	Duration
Prof. Dr. Anke Weidlich 0000-0003-2361-0912	UFR, Freiburg	TA2, TA4, TA5, TA6 , TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Reinhard German 0000-0002-9071-4802	FAU, Erlangen	TA1, TA3, TA4, TA5 , TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Johan Lilliestam 0000-0001-6913-5956	FAU, Nürnberg	TA2, TA4, TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Christof Weinhardt 0000-0002-7945-4077	KIT, Karlsruhe	TA1, TA2 , TA3, TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Veit Hagenmeyer 0000-0002-3572-9083	KIT, Karlsruhe	TA2, TA4, TA5, TA6, TA7	02/2023 -

Prof. Dr. Sebastian Lehnhoff 0000-0003-2340-6807	OFFIS, Oldenburg	TA1, TA4 , TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Antonello Monti, Ph.D. 0000-0003-1914-9801	RWTH, Aachen	TA3 , TA4, TA5, TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Berthold Vogel	SOFI, Göttingen	TA1, TA2, TA6, TA7	02/2023 -
Prof. Dr. Sören Auer 0000-0002-0698-2864	TIB, Hannover	TA4, TA7	02/2023 -

▪ Participants

Participating institutions	Location	Duration
Reiner Lemoine Institut gGmbH (RLI)	Berlin	02/2023 -
Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fraunhofer Institut für angewandte Informationstechnik (FhFIT) 	München Aachen	02/2023 -
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institut für vernetzte Energiesysteme 	Köln Stuttgart	12/2024 -
Institut für Angewandte Informatik (InfAI) e.V. An-Institut an der Universität Leipzig	Leipzig	12/2024 -
Universität Osnabrück (UOS)	Osnabrück	12/2024 -
Öko-Institut e.V. (ÖKO)	Freiburg	02/2025 -

Part B2

1 Consortium

As NFDI4Energy, we aim to make data and software the scientific foundation for a sustainable energy future ([our vision](#)). Good research data management (RDM) in energy research is key for the **interdisciplinary collaboration** that is essential to tackle the technical, economic, social, and policy dimensions of the energy transition. By ensuring that research outputs are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), RDM will simplify the use of artificial intelligence, shorten innovation cycles, reduce duplication, foster excellent research, and drive the scientific advances needed for a sustainable energy future.

Based on our joint vision, we detailed the following mission for all energy research:

We empower energy researchers to manage, reuse, develop, publish, and communicate data and software throughout the research process. To achieve this, we train and support energy researchers in research data management and research software engineering through our services that are available in our quality-assured portfolio. By continuously improving these services, we ensure simple usability for all stakeholders. Through close partnership with industry, society, and public administration, we make additional required data available and reusable for research. This collaboration benefits industry, society, policy, and public administration by providing accessible, comprehensive, evidence-based information. Together, we advance energy research and work towards a secure, sustainable energy future where data drives progress.

This mission guided our consortium, which focuses on the community of energy system research during its first funding phase:

- We established **energy research data management (ERDM)** as a relevant topic in the energy system research community through different outreach and community activities on a national ([Section 1.1](#)) and international ([Section 1.3](#)) level, to foster shorter innovation cycles, less redundancy, and higher quality of data as needed for energy system innovations.
- **Jointly developing showcases**, we both understood our community's needs and showcased best RDM practices. Besides scientific partners, we also involved other relevant stakeholders from **society, public administration, and industry** in our efforts.
- Thanks to our strong commitment to oneNFDI, our consortium benefits greatly from the overall NFDI, for example by using and tailoring base services and existing services of other consortia ([Section 1.2](#)). As part of oneNFDI, we took leading roles and responsibilities in NFDI committees (see DFG Data sheet ID 1011) and additionally participated in multiple discussions around the strategy and further development of the NFDI, which also influenced our development of operating strategies ([Section 1.5](#)) and made these discussions available to our community.
- To effectively organize our work towards our mission, we built **agile structures** ([Section 1.4](#)).

1.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

RDM does not have a long-standing tradition in energy system research. At the beginning of our first funding phase, most energy system researchers had only limited knowledge of RDM. We started our consortium with one large infrastructure provider (TIB), one domain-specific infrastructure provider (RLI), and nine leading research groups in energy system research. Five of these research groups had prior experience with domain-specific ontologies and (simulation) infrastructure. To further develop our consortium, we built on the structures of the NFDI association and extended our consortium by integrating new members to [our consortium in the association](#) (*Konsortium gemäß Satzung* (KgS)) from energy system research in Germany. Over the years, we added 16 new members to the KgS (universities, universities of applied sciences, other research institutions), and we plan further extensions to better involve our community. As a KgS, our cooperation is based on a jointly-developed [commitment for RDM](#) [1]. We also used our flex funds ([Section 4.2](#)) to further support the integration of new members and [additional ERDM projects](#).

As a means to evolve our community, discuss relevant ERDM topics, and involve new stakeholders, we started the yearly **NFDI4Energy Conference**, designed as a conference at the intersection between energy system research and RDM. At [the first conference in Hanover \(2024\)](#) with more than 120 participants, 53% of the attendees had not been involved in NFDI4Energy but represented large parts of the German energy system research community, including large research organizations like Fraunhofer Gesellschaft and Helmholtz. The program included workshops, 17 presentations, and highly interactive poster sessions. In an effort to emphasize the community-driven nature of the conference by rotating its venues, Karlsruhe was deliberately chosen as the location for the [2025 edition](#) (participants shown in Figure 1).

Our (co-)spokespersons are **embedded in multiple energy system research communities**. Many of them (Astrid Nieße, Veit Hagenmeyer, Anke Weidlich, and Sebastian Lehnhoff) are deeply engaged in the Energy Informatics community ([GI Special Interest Group \(SIG\) “Energy Informatics”](#), [DACH+ conference on energy informatics](#), [ACM SIGEnergy](#), and its flagship conference [ACM e-Energy](#)).

Figure 1 Participants of the second NFDI4Energy Conference

Additionally, our co-spokespersons Anke Weidlich and Sebastian Lehnhoff are on the board of directors in the national initiative “[Energy Systems of the Future](#)” (ESYS) of the German Academies of Sciences, which brings together leading scientists working on the energy transition. Our co-spokesperson Johan Lilliestam is appointed as one of the lead authors for the seventh assessment report of the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)](#) as part of his focus on empirical research on climate and energy policy effectiveness. The involvement of our co-spokespersons and partners in these and other relevant organizations in Germany (e.g., BDI, VDE, BITKOM, VolkswagenStiftung, Dateninstitut) has extended our visibility.

Wolfgang Süß, part of the team of Veit Hagenmeyer, is the coordinator for the [hub energy of the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration \(HMC\)](#). He successfully synchronizes our activities with the activities of HMC, e.g., results from HMC surveys were integrated into the requirements analysis for metadata. Many of our members (e.g., RLI, ÖKO) are also active members of the [Open Energy Family](#), which develops different RDM tools such as the Open Energy Database.

Interaction with relevant DFG research activities, like Priority Programs, DFG CRC/Transregio, and DFG Research Training Groups (e.g., [CAUSE](#)) has been started by offering focused ERDM talks (DFG Fachgruppentreffen, DFG RTG Summer Schools, [DFG Collaborative Research Centre 1404](#), etc.). We are also in contact with the [Cluster of Excellence PoLIS](#), since we plan to cover the whole energy research community in the second funding phase with the goal of sharing knowledge and solutions to benefit all parties.

On a state level, we are especially involved in the energy system research activities in Lower Saxony, which are coordinated by the [Energieforschungszentrum Niedersachsen](#) (Energy Research Centre of the federal state of Lower Saxony, EFZN). We actively support them in integrating RDM practices into their flagship project [TEN.efzn](#).

In all these communities, our co-spokespersons and staff work continuously to improve RDM practices and increase the visibility of NFDI4Energy by acting as multipliers. We **joined over 120 events** (see DFG Data sheet ID 1009) to achieve these goals by presenting and discussing our concepts and solutions:

- in more than 20 invited talks and keynotes, e.g., at the [ETG Congress 2023](#)
- with posters or conference booths at over 12 energy-specific events, e.g., at [DACH Energy Informatics](#), Leibniz University Hanover: [Tag der Energieforschung](#)
- with posters at over 10 local RDM events, e.g., in [Göttingen](#), [Bremen](#)
- as part of over 50 scientific presentations

We are especially involved in multiple events of the [Forschungsnetzwerke Energie](#), which organizes different activities around energy research for the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWE). We joined events of the network on buildings, the network on energy system analysis, and of the overall structure (e.g., [Energieforschungskonferenz](#)), and presented NFDI4Energy with keynotes, posters, booths, and other formats.

In addition to our involvement at events, we rely on **social media** to connect with researchers and share news, e.g., [LinkedIn](#) (> 750 followers). Also, we highlight important activities in a quarterly email [newsletter](#).

Together with our [Scientific Advisory Board \(SAB\)](#), these community activities are also crucial for understanding and gathering the concrete **needs of researchers**, e.g., relevant requirements for our services. This strategy of communication and needs assessment via events and social media was supplemented by a study with energy system researchers in Germany, combining a workshop and 15 semi-structured expert interviews [2]. These systematic outcomes were involved in the development of our RDM strategy ([Section 2](#)).

To include a **societal perspective**, we actively engage with data journalists to identify relevant data needs for journalistic activities. In this context, we participated in the [SciCAR conference 2025](#). Additionally, we experimented with formats to engage non-academic audiences in RDM topics through citizen-oriented events, such as the “Tag der offenen Tür” at KIT and the “Effekte Woche” in Karlsruhe. Furthermore, as the **public administration** is an important data provider for energy research, we started discussions with the [Bundesnetzagentur \(BNetzA\)](#) to improve data availability for energy researchers. With this activity, we better understand current barriers and different requirements regarding FAIR data, which was one of our major responsibilities in the first two years of NFDI4Energy.

To involve **industry** in our consortium and to better address the challenges of data sharing between energy research and energy industry, we established an industry network with 21 members. This network includes representatives from energy producers, energy suppliers, network operators, technology providers, IT companies, and consulting firms. We used this network to conduct a first workshop, which led to an initial set of requirements [3]. We integrated these requirements in our further developments, e.g., regarding tooling for data anonymization. Furthermore, we established an [Industry Advisory Board \(IAB\)](#) with representatives from different organizations like network operators, equipment and software providers (e.g., Siemens Energy), and energy suppliers (e.g., E.ON). The board meets once per year to advise on priorities. Finally, we presented NFDI4Energy at the E-world exhibition, where we directly discussed data sharing practices with industry stakeholders.

1.2 The consortium within the NFDI / General Contribution to the development of the NFDI

We have actively engaged in shaping and supporting the development of oneNFDI, e.g., with our spokesperson and coordinators. One key contribution is through Astrid Nieße’s role as the **speaker in the NFDI Strategy Committee** within the association (KVAS, Strategieausschuss der Konsortialversammlung), where the concrete actions to translate the NFDI strategy to measures for the next two years are discussed and prioritized. Moreover, the consortium is an active member of the **Task Force on Governance and Sustainability** [4], which aims to ensure the long-

term viability, financing, and usefulness of NFDI infrastructures. The consortium actively contributes towards collaborative work in NFDI, with a detailed overview in [5]. These involvements help to align internal strategies with broader NFDI goals and ensure that the perspective of energy research is included in oneNFDI.

With RDM being a relevant topic for all scientific domains, our consortium is engaged in many activities in this context, leading to additional involvement in other NFDI consortia. We briefly recap the **institutional involvement**, without mentioning the personal activities of our co-spokespersons, in Table 1.

Table 1 Overview of institutional involvement of our partners in other NFDI consortia

Institution	Co-applicant / applicant (in bold)	Participant
UFR	NFDI4BIOIMAGE	NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Culture, Text+, NFDI-MatWerk, GHGA, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Earth, PUNCH4NFDI
UOL	None	None
FAU	NFDI-MatWerk, DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRmat, NFDI4Cat	NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Earth
KIT	NFDI4Ing, KonsortSWD, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4CS, DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRmat, NFDI4Cat, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Earth, PUNCH4NFDI	NFDI4Microbiota
TIB	NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4DS, NFDI4Chem	NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Microbiota, FAIRmat, NFDI4Earth, PUNCH4NFDI
OFFIS		NFDI4Health
RWTH	NFDI4Ing, NFDI4DS, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4CS, NFDI4Microbiota, DAPHNE4NFDI, NFDI4Cat, NFDI4Chem	NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Earth, PUNCH4NFDI
SOFI	None	None
DLR	NFDI4Ing	NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Microbiota, PUNCH4NFDI
Fraunhofer	NFDI4DataScience, NFDI-Matwerk, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Cat, MaRDI	NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Microbiota
InfAI	None	NFDI4Biodiversity
UOS	NFDI4BIOIMAGE	None

We **successfully integrated other consortia in our community efforts**. As an example, we established a market of consortia format (with NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Ing, NFDI-Matwerk, KonsortSWD, BERD@NFDI, NFDI4Datascience, Text+, Base4NFDI) that has been very well received as a fixed part of our conference programs. At our first conference, Barbara Ebert, spokesperson of NFDI4Biodiversity, gave a keynote sharing insights on the experiences of already-established consortia and communities. Additionally, we participated in several conferences and workshops of other consortia and established meaningful partnerships, e.g., with NFDI-MatWerk and KonsortSWD.

Figure 2 NFDI4Energy team at CoRDI 2025

The **Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI)** is the main venue to establish new connections among the NFDI consortia and the German RDM communities. As NFDI4Energy, we were highly integrated in CoRDI 2023 and 2025 (as shown in Figure 2), with contributions such as talks and posters. We established CoRDI as a learning and networking opportunity for our young researchers in this area, and successfully invited researchers from our international energy informatics community to this event.

While CoRDI is an important venue for discussing cross-cutting topics, we also joined the discussion of cross-cutting topics in the NFDI sections, for example in the section “(Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance” [6]. Within that section, we further fostered the creation of a new working group on research software metadata [7] since research software is an important research artifact for our consortium. This working group was later co-led by an NFDI4Energy member. Our activities in this working group led to our participation in the base service `nfdi.software` and the already kicked-off DFG project ConnOSS [8] as a joint activity from NFDI4Energy, NFDI4DataScience, and KonsortSWD. Overall, we learn from others, collaborate when possible and join the important steps to harmonize the RDM approaches between the consortia **towards oneNFDI**.

The NFDI sections are the foundation for the **development of base services** within Base4NFDI, a joint project of all NFDI consortia. As a consortium, we support Base4NFDI, regularly exchange with their service stewards, and have joined all **Base User Conferences**. Within NFDI4Energy, we actively use and benefit from multiple base services. Via IAM4NFDI, we integrate the common identity and access management into multiple services (namely the OEDB and the LDM). We also offer a RDMO instance via DMP4NFDI. Initial exchanges with PID4NFDI have begun, marking early steps toward integrating persistent identifiers (PIDs) within NFDI4Energy.

While the usage of these services improves the interoperability within the NFDI, we also see it as an important step for further interoperability on a **European level**. Through the high involvement of Base4NFDI in the EOSC, we will also further profit from using the base services in our consortium for our internationalization efforts.

1.3 International networking

Within the reporting period, we implemented several steps towards international networking and embedding our activities with already-established international networks. The main learning from the funding phase so far has been that the **established international networks of our energy system research community** and involved institutions (IEEE, IEC, ACM SIGEnergy) are the best starting points for reflecting and disseminating our services on an international level.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) plays an important role in these activities and is a key player in RDM on a European level. Thus, as a regular task for networking and dissemination, we actively participated through poster presentations and booths at the EOSC symposia in 2023-2025. The TIB Terminology Service, integrated in our NFDI4Energy service portfolio, is part of the **EOSC-NFDI Node** development through TS4NFDI, fostering our role within the overall contributions of NFDI to EOSC.

Additionally, third-party funding activities have been pushed in the EOSC context. NFDI4Energy institutions (OFFIS, TIB) collaborated in the joint EOSC project **“Using Generative AI (GenAI4EU) for Scientific Research via EOSC”**.

We started further **European networking and dissemination activities** with participation in events with varying formats. At the third general assembly of [int:net](#), October 2024 in Brussels we presented NFDI4Energy [9]; we also joined the Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop by [ERIGRID 2.0](#) in Roskilde, Denmark [10], as well as the Energy Transition Week (NTNU 2024). Invited keynotes on the vision and mission of NFDI4Energy have been given at several conferences and workshops, e.g., [OSMSES 2024](#) (Vienna) and [DigiSect 2025](#) (Stockholm). In addition, we collaborate with members from other initiatives like [iDesignRES](#) and [Man0EUVre](#) [11].

On a **global level**, activities within the community of the [ACM SIGEnergy](#) (ACM Special Interest Group Energy) have been used to both collect requirements and disseminate results. As an example, a joint workshop with international representatives ([6th International Workshop on Energy Data and Analytics \(EDA\)](#)) took place at the ACM e-Energy in Rotterdam (2025). The workshop enriched an existing workshop series on data analytics with an additional ERDM perspective. The workshop adaptation was well received by the target audience and will be continued in 2026 at ACM e-Energy in Banff, Canada. With this and other activities, NFDI4Energy’s ideas have been discussed with researchers from Australia, Asia, and North America in existing networks and beyond.

We have introduced our good ERDM practices to international activities in journals and conference proceedings. As an example, the ACM SIGEnergy’s [Energy Informatics Review](#) adapted its templates to better reflect data and software availability, and also integrated FAIR aspects into its review guidelines.

In addition, we put emphasis on ensuring an international composition of the **SAB** to include international views and reflections on recent progress on RDM and energy system research.

1.4 Organizational structure and viability / sustainability

Figure 3 Updated overview of the task areas

For efficient activities within NFDI4Energy, we structure the work in eight **task areas**, which are summarized in Figure 3. Each task area is supervised by a co-spokesperson and is coordinated by a task area lead. In contrast to the original proposal, we aggregated data services and other core services into a new Task Area 8, which allowed a better integration of flex projects into the structure. The flex projects are small projects with a short runtime, which we funded through our flex funds (Section 4.2).

To guide the work in NFDI4Energy and its involvement in oneNFDI, we use two dedicated boards. The **steering committee (SC)** consists of the (co-)spokespersons, the lead coordinator, and representatives of all participants. The SC is responsible for all decisions related to the funded work program, e.g., finances and the progress report. To deeply involve our community, we also use the **KgS** as an additional steering board in NFDI4Energy, strengthening the community involvement. This round decides on strategic aspects like the vision and mission. Both the KgS and the SC meet twice a year. The KgS has delegated some decisions to dedicated committees whose compositions are voted on by the KgS:

- The **flex fund committee** is responsible for the decision on flex project proposals.
- The **base service committee** decides on the vote of NFDI4Energy in the regular votes on new **base service proposals**.
- The **service committee** evaluates whether services fulfill the requirements to become NFDI4Energy candidate services or NFDI4Energy services (Section 2.4).

We have also set up two additional boards to provide us with advice and guidance: the already introduced **IAB** and **SAB** (Section 1.1). These boards comprise additional experts in the fields of

FAIR research data, research software engineering, and energy system research. Every year, we present and discuss our progress with the SAB. We received meaningful feedback from the board which we incorporated in our further development.

To support the different boards and the work in the task areas, as well as to coordinate the activities in NFDI4Energy, we set up a central **coordination office** staffed by the UOL and OFFIS (Task Area 7). While we originally planned to have only one person for the coordination, we adapted the resources for the coordination office based on learnings from other consortia, e.g., by shifting the original planned flex funds to the coordination office and making use of in-kind contributions. The coordination office now consists of **five persons** (partly part-time, 3 funded Full-Time Equivalents (FTEs) and 0.5 FTE in-kind): (1) a lead coordinator responsible for overall coordination and NFDI involvement, (2) a co-coordinator responsible for community involvement and internationalization, (3) a finance coordinator responsible for distributing funding to our partners, (4) an outreach coordinator responsible for coordinating event participants and social media, and (5) a service coordinator responsible for the service process ([Section 2.4](#)). This updated structure allows for continuity, improved knowledge management, and the ability to respond proactively to emerging needs.

1.5 Operating model

Our work in NFDI4Energy tackles a critical gap in energy research in Germany. From our perspective, the consortium and its services require two different types of operating models. As a consequence, we differentiate between these aspects in the following text.

Regarding the **operating model of the consortium**, and especially its community-involving aspects, we currently use the KgS as the main instrument to guide the work and to integrate different users. Therefore, we have substantially increased the size of the KgS ([Section 1.1](#)). We aim to further improve the differentiation between this instrument and the SC within this funding phase. Generally, we focus on and participate in the current discussions around the long-term perspective of the NFDI association. We see a high need to sustainably include our community-involving aspects in the NFDI association.

Regarding the **services** ([Section 2.4](#)), we aim to develop specific operating models for all services in our portfolio. Thus, we discuss on a per-service basis the kind of operating model that is needed for maintenance in a sustainable way. **Possible operating models** for these services include institutional funding (e.g., through Leibniz Association, Helmholtz Association, or federal state's funding), regular subsidies from the NFDI association, usage fees, membership models, or some combination of these. Additional project-based short-term funding can be used to develop new services or raise Technical Readiness Levels (TRLs), but not to sustainably maintain, host, and

quality-assure them. Any chosen solution must ensure that all researchers in Germany have reliable access to the developed service landscape. We engage in NFDI discussions regarding this topic to learn from other consortia and harmonize our efforts.

Currently all our services are offered free of charge, as a result of the funding from NFDI4Energy and in-kind contributions of our co-applicants. This situation lowers entry barriers and supports cultural change toward the adoption of ERDM practices. While introducing fees too early may risk slowing down this process by creating hurdles, a sufficiently strong and clearly communicated value proposition can also motivate users to accept such costs once tangible benefits are evident, offering another possible avenue for long-term funding. Our service portfolio and the starting process of labeling services as NFDI4Energy services will allow us to directly discuss possible operating models with the current service operators.

In some cases, the current operator will be unable to fulfill all requirements to become a labeled NFDI4Energy service, e.g., in terms of sustainable operation. In these cases, a switch to a new operator is a possible step towards finding a suitable operating model. Currently, we are in the process of switching the operation of the Open Energy Database to our partner OFFIS to allow for a more sustainable operating model. The process is set up in a manner that allows us to derive important learnings and thus establish a blueprint for service transfer.

2 Research Data Management Strategy

Good RDM enables **better interdisciplinary research**, while interdisciplinarity is important for energy system research. To better understand the detailed needs of this diverse group of researchers and to illustrate the relevance of our services for RDM, we developed multiple **show-cases** in our consortium which show the possible application of RDM practices as supported by our services ([Section 2.1](#)).

The development and operation of quality-assured services is our main method to improve and support RDM for energy system research. To give researchers and infrastructure-providers clear orientation, we established a precise process to develop, enhance, and quality-assure services in our **service portfolio** ([Section 2.4](#)). Our portfolio consists of existing services which we have successfully integrated into the portfolio, services improved in the consortium, and services developed in the consortium.

Metadata standards and ontologies are the foundation to unlock the full potential of our services. We extend existing approaches to address the requirements of energy system researchers, and develop new metadata schemas and ontologies where needed ([Section 2.2](#)).

While metadata are an essential part of making **research data FAIR**, we see additional aspects like **data quality** as relevant to achieve reusability ([Section 2.3](#)).

In energy system research, simulation of components and networks with the help of research software is a core research method. As a consequence, we identified that energy system research

benefits from the findings of research software engineering (RSE), and started to build up the topic of **energy research software engineering** (Section 2.5).

2.1 Scientific relevance and quality of the measures

First, we recap the **adaptations of our work plan**: At the beginning of NFDI4Energy, we followed the task area structure and work plan as outlined in the funding proposal. However, after onboarding completion, it became evident that service development required a more focused approach to meet growing demands effectively and enable more communication between different service developers. As a result, a new Task Area 8, *Data and Core Services*, was established. This change enabled more efficient handling of key technical topics, such as data infrastructures, interfaces, and service provision. Decision-making processes were streamlined, and meeting frequency reduced. In general, we follow a strategy of **continuous and agile adaption of the work plan and the consortium's governance** (Section 1.3).

In the funding proposal, we described use cases (e.g., *flexibility usage in energy systems*) to demonstrate **good RDM practices fostering excellent research**. To better highlight service usage and the relevance for our scientific community, we divided the use cases into **smaller showcases** that depict **best practices and success stories** of RDM through our services, thereby showing examples of what our services are good for (described in detail in Section 2.4). They should serve as blueprints for energy system researchers and will be systematically **communicated to our community** at different events and through a future virtual roadshow. Below, we highlight **four of our current six showcases**:

One showcase demonstrates how incidents that threaten energy system functionality can be easily **compared** using the **ORKG** [12, 13]. This serves as a practical example of how the ORKG can turn scientific literature into a searchable, comparable knowledge base. To facilitate the usage of the ORKG, we also produced two short videos: a benefits overview and a step-by-step tutorial [14]. The tutorial shows researchers how to upload a paper, enrich it with semantic metadata, and generate a state-of-the-art comparison.

Another showcase displays how streamlined long-term energy scenario data enable better **comparability and analysis of long-term energy scenarios** within the **Open Energy Scenario Bundles** [15]. The qualitative comparison allows users to filter by scenario type, time horizon, region, and more. We have already added around 50 annotated scenarios to the Open Energy Scenario Bundles. The showcase also explains how additional data can be easily annotated using the **NFDI4Energy annotator** (part of the TIB Terminology Service) and the **Open Energy Ontology (OEO)**.

A next showcase demonstrates planning of good RDM in an energy system research project on self-healing flexibility aggregation in future energy systems, by creating data management plans in **RDMO4Energy** [16].

[Another showcase](#) investigates the empirical knowledge base for climate policies [17]. For the final sprint towards the Paris Agreement targets, knowing which policies work is essential. For this, we developed the **Climate and Energy Policy Ontology (CEPO)** and collected curated data (first version in the [Climate Policy Atlas](#)). By comparing this ontology-annotated FAIR data with a systematic literature review of the empirical climate policy literature, we showed that policy effectiveness data is highly skewed: there is empirical insight about carbon pricing and renewable power support in Europe, the US, and China, but almost no evaluation of other policy instruments or other countries. In sum, this suggests that climate policy efforts so far are implemented based on expectations but less on scientific evidence, which may turn into a problem as climate ambitions tighten in the coming years.

Besides our showcases, our work program has already led to **additional relevant outcomes** which especially highlight the involvement of different stakeholder groups in RDM:

With our services, we want to support actors who mediate between scientific data and public or political audiences, such as **data journalists and NGOs**. As one example for this purpose, we launched the [Climate Policy Atlas](#), which allows exploration of national policies with easy-to-understand visualizations. The launch in January 2026 included civil society organizations and policymakers. As direct science-to-society communication is rarely systematic or sustainable, we focus on enabling these mediators to reuse and communicate research data more effectively. Based on interviews and workshops with data journalists [18], we identified requirements for communicating energy data in ways that facilitate reuse in journalistic contexts (publication forthcoming).

Our services should also support interaction between **industry** and research. To enable a two-way flow of FAIR data between those worlds, we have drafted a provisional process for data contribution and access [19], which will be refined together with our industry network. We will especially concentrate on (i) accessibility of sensitive data and (ii) the fitting provenance level for reuse as our next steps.

Through our services, it should be easier to **integrate non-technical data** (e.g., consumer preferences, behavioral incentives, and policy contexts) into energy modeling to achieve new research results by increasing the societal realism and policy relevance of the models [20]. To better determine how this research data need to be prepared, we first concentrated on the systematic collection of parameters and concepts that describe demand-side behavior, where non-technical factors are decisive [21–23]. At the same time, we explored how ontologies can be used to embed these non-technical data into energy system models [24].

2.2 Metadata standards and reliable services

In contrast to many other research domains, data publication and the use of metadata to describe data have only a few sporadic examples in the energy domain, and there are not yet any **widely**

adopted data services to support this, as has already been pointed out by Wierling et al. [25]. Due to its interdisciplinary nature, energy system research uses highly diverse data: from laws and economic data, to interview and survey data, to technical data from measurements and simulations. Therefore, we first identified data management solutions that focused on similar data types in other research domains and NFDI consortia. We used them as blueprints where possible. We decided to make use of ontologies and semantic metadata from the beginning for any newly-established RDM process or service within NFDI4Energy.

To understand the state-of-the-art regarding metadata standards and associated solutions, we actively participate in the NFDI section “(Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance” [6], especially in the workshops of the Task Force Metadata. Moreover, we have reviewed many publications of NFDI consortia and beyond on the strategies and metadata standards used for any kind of use case [26]. Additionally, we investigated the metadata standard list of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) as well as additional entries in fairsharing.org to classify the relevance of those standards for metadata in the energy domain [26]. Those insights were used to define a **set of technical requirements for metadata schemas**, metadata records, and services that use metadata [27]. Among the many different metadata approaches that exist, we encourage the use of **semantic metadata** (RDF-based) over more traditional solutions, as this directly enables semantic interoperability. Therefore, all metadata records should be validated against their schema whenever a system interacts with a new set of metadata. The **storage of metadata** needs to align with the respective use case. Therefore, we do not enforce the use of triple stores as metadata storage systems. However, we provide SPARQL endpoints for multiple services, like the ORKG, the LDM, the Open Energy Database, and the Open Energy Databus.

To be **aligned with oneNFDI in terms of metadata**, we also require the use or export of one of the three basic metadata standards: DataCite, DCAT-AP, and schema.org [28]. However, for domain-specific use cases these need to be extended with domain-specific metadata. Many domain-specific metadata modules can be generalized to support multiple domains. On this topic, we are collaborating with other consortia like NFDI4Ing and NFDI4Chem to develop metadata tooling and modules that can be reused beyond NFDI4Energy. One unresolved challenge which we are currently addressing together is the creation of a **generic and machine-actionable solution to metadata schema conversion** for existing metadata records. If solved, this can greatly improve interoperability and metadata harvesting.

We contribute to the improvement of the **Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata) standard** [29], by aligning it with our requirements for metadata [27] and by defining more modular metadata to address different types of energy data.

Regarding metadata for energy research software, we developed the metadata schema **ERSmeta** [30, 31], which is based on CodeMeta, a common metadata standard for research software. Together with NFDI4Ing, we investigated how software interfaces can be described with

research software metadata [32]. We are highly active in the NFDI working group on research software metadata [7] and related discussions in the deRSE.

To achieve semantic metadata, fitting **ontologies** are required to define the necessary terminologies needed in a metadata context. Therefore, we established a collection of ontologies relevant for the energy systems sector, which is available as a [collection on the Terminology Service](#). While this collection presents a good starting point, we extended existing ontologies and created new ontologies where needed, to enable energy system researchers to meaningfully annotate their data.

We use the domain-specific **Open Energy Ontology (OEO)** as a core ontology. It was developed as an open source project by a diverse community on GitHub [33] and provides a standardized terminology for indexing research data in the energy sector. The development of the OEO is guided by a steering committee, which meets approximately every two months. As NFDI4Energy, we took over the responsibility for the organization of this committee, which includes representatives from 12 German institutions involved with the OEO. This group aims to increase awareness and adoption of the ontology among the energy research community.

Our contributions to the OEO include concepts for the modeling of long-term energy system scenarios. Additionally, we defined core concepts about **simulation scenarios** aiming to formalize essential terms and relationships relevant to simulation-based studies. Efforts are underway to integrate these into the OEO to promote standardization and reusability. Thereby, the OEO will serve as a harmonized interface across different co-simulation frameworks. Furthermore, we plan to integrate concepts for describing power grids as part of this ontology, e.g., by integrating industry standards from IEC TC57 like the Common Information Model (CIM). The main hurdle for the harmonization is the lack of openness for the relevant set of standards, while we see benefits that could come from integrating these ontological developments.

Along with our OEO work, we created a new **Climate and Energy Policy Ontology (CEPO)**, which is designed for interoperability with the OEO. This ontology helps users systematically record interoperable data on climate policy instruments such as zoning and planning regulations and economic incentives. Ontology-annotated data enables better analyses, including integration of real regulatory policies into models and measurement of policy effectiveness (see [Section 2.1](#) for first results from this activity).

To achieve an interoperable environment for new and existing energy-related ontologies, we established the **Energy-related Reference Ontologies (ENERO) Foundry**. This foundry sets forth principles for ontology development and will examine ontologies for their compliance with these principles, to ensure that energy system researchers have access to high-quality ontologies.

To synchronize our activities with others, we presented our metadata and ontology developments in multiple scientific publications [34–47]. The different metadata schemas and ontologies are used and included into different services (see [48] and [Section 2.4](#) for details).

2.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

We drive the implementation of the FAIR principles with dedicated standardization activities ([Section 2.2](#)) and service developments ([Section 2.4](#)). In the following, we discuss how we implemented the FAIR principles and draw connections to our service development. A detailed description of the service portfolio is given in [Section 2.4](#).

Finding relevant research data (**Findability**) is facilitated by the use of PIDs assigned to metadata, which are explicitly linked to their corresponding datasets. The LDM enables this process by assigning DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and incorporating internal identifiers within metadata, which are rendered searchable through a knowledge graph. In a similar manner, the ORKG facilitates the creation and publication of comparisons of published research, accompanied by DOIs, ensuring that the comparisons can be discovered through a web interface or REST API. Similarly, metadata foster findability within the Open Energy Database and Open Energy Scenario Bundles: these services use the OEMetadata Standard and register all metadata in the Open Energy Databus. The new service SMECS ([Section 2.4](#)) enhances findability and interoperability of research software by generating metadata based on the relevant metadata schemas CodeMeta and ERSmeta.

The requirement of **Accessibility** is centered on the maintenance of access using metadata. This is achieved by retrieving metadata using standard communication protocols, despite the data itself being unavailable. The LDM fulfills this requirement through the implementation of HTTP(S)-based queries of metadata. The ORKG and the Open Energy Database facilitate independent retrieval of metadata and data via their user interfaces and their REST interfaces.

In terms of **Interoperability**, the FAIR principles prescribe the use of formal, shared languages and vocabularies, metadata that itself follows FAIR principles, and qualified references to other (meta)data. To meet these requirements, all metadata of the LDM are described in terms of Dublin Core and DCAT and are available in various RDF serializations. Additionally, datasets in the LDM can be linked to publications in the ORKG that either define or use them. The ORKG supports the use of ontologies, like the OEO, to describe its research comparisons. Data exports are available in RDF and can be queried via SPARQL.

Reusability encompasses the principles of clear licensing, evident provenance, and adherence to community standards. The LDM supports licensing metadata and limited provenance information, with plans to integrate domain-relevant standards through formats such as RO-Crate. In the ORKG, data is published with a CC-BY SA license. As shown in [Section 2.2](#), we are actively involved in the development of community standards.

The alignment of RDM services with FAIR standards demonstrates the progress achieved in this area. In terms of providing **measurable and neutral results**, three services have been examined using the [FAIR Checker](#): the LDM, the ORKG, and the Open Energy Database. We randomly selected a number of datasets managed via these services and analyzed them using this tool.

The ORKG obtained the best average dataset score of 83%, followed by the Open Energy Database with 75% and the LDM with 67%. These mean values serve as indicators for the FAIR-compliant provision of research data via the services. Generally, the implementation of PIDs in all services did not completely meet the requirements of the FAIR Checker, since the checker includes life-science-specific requirements for PIDs. The LDM receives full marks with regard to the 'Accessible' criterion. As required metadata fields were not available, 'Interoperability' led to a downgrading. In comparison, the ORKG achieved the highest score, getting full marks for the principles 'Accessible' and 'Reusable'. The Open Energy Database did not fulfill the requirements regarding the 'Findable' criterion, as it does not yet provide PIDs. The presented shortcomings in all services will be examined in more detail and remedied in the second half of this funding phase. With respect to **data quality assurance**, a process has to be defined within the consortium in the second part of this funding phase. The process will be able to build on several aspects of our services which we have already included for the purpose of data quality assurance. One such aspect in the ORKG is the requirement for users to register with the service prior to adding or modifying data. Additionally, all managed data are licensed under CC0 1.0, and only limited personal data (email and password) are stored using Keycloak for secure authentication. A responsible Data Protection Officer is identified in the respective institution, and users can opt in to usage statistics. Taking a different approach, both the Open Energy Database and the Open Energy Scenario Bundles integrate IAM4NFDI. Personal data are handled with state-of-the-art technologies. Nevertheless, adaptations are necessary to ensure both data quality and security. The Open Energy Database and the Open Energy Scenario Bundles have no Data Protection Officers, do not license all stored data, and do not allow users to opt out of usage statistics. In a middle ground between these approaches lies the LDM service, which requires registration for certain functions (like the ORKG) and also integrates IAM4NFDI (like the Open Energy Database and Open Energy Scenario Bundles). It licenses all managed data, stores no personal data on its servers, and has a Data Protection Officer.

In summary, our services already provide significant valuable support for FAIR data management, but show areas for relevant improvement. The LDM and Open Energy Database focus on ensuring data quality and consistency through structured workflows, while the ORKG facilitates the collaborative creation, comparison, and integration of research knowledge.

2.4 Services provided by the consortium

Closely aligned to the discussions on a NFDI service portfolio [49], we have defined requirements and a service onboarding process to guarantee the reliability of NFDI4Energy services. The process consists of two stages with different requirements to become a *Candidate Service* and a full *NFDI4Energy Service*. The full process is shown in Figure 4 and defined in detail in [50]. Part of the requirements is the use of standardized APIs, improving the interoperability of the services,

and their integration with additional services and workflows. Additionally, we require our services to use relevant metadata schemas and ontologies as discussed in [Section 2.2](#).

Figure 4 NFDI4Energy service process

We see the following types of services in our portfolio:

- existing services further developed to meet our requirements, e.g., by tailoring to the domain of energy systems (foundation domain-specific or non-domain-specific);
- existing energy-specific services without adaptation (We currently have no services of this type.);
- new services developed by our consortium.

Besides these types of services, we see also a potential need to increase the usage of certain domain-agnostic services if they add value to research processes in energy system research. These services will not be included into our portfolio, but we will link them to the overall NFDI service portfolio, which is in development as part of the [NFDI strategy](#).

All services are available as open source software and are currently **operated as in-kind contributions** since no funding was available for operating (i.e., hardware and technical staff). These operations are partly based on the **institutional mission of the responsible institution**, which we will highlight explicitly in the following, if applicable. Generally, finding a sustainable operator for a service remains a challenge and is closely linked to discussions on suitable operating models ([Section 1.5](#)).

Our [currently-operating services](#) address different phases of the research data lifecycle, as shown in Figure 5. We give further details on each service in the following.

The **TIB Terminology Service** provides a single point of access to terminologies from multiple domain, including energy. It is an underlying infrastructure service, which is used both by **knowledge engineers** (through a search interface accessible from the browser or built into other applications using the API) and by other

NFDI4Energy services. From a technical perspective, the Terminology Service indexes multiple ontologies and vocabularies, exposing their term sets, hierarchies, synonyms, and translations via a RESTful API built on the open-source Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) framework; clients can then query, retrieve and embed concept metadata. The main improvements through NFDI4Energy are the **integration of energy-related ontologies** (like the OEO), the inclusion of user feedback from integrating the service into the **Open Energy Scenario Bundles** and the **LDM**, and the **development of further features** for the automated indexing of scientific texts.

Figure 5 NFDI4Energy services and their placement in the RDM lifecycle

The **RDMO4Energy** service implements an instance of the RDM Organizer (RDMO), a tool for developing and completing data management plans (e.g., in the form of questionnaires or step-by-step wizards). From a user perspective, RDMO4Energy allows researchers and institutions to create their own **data management plans** using templates provided by funding agencies, adapting them as their projects progress. The resulting forms can be exported in a variety of formats. Data administrators can collaborate on data projects and benefit from role and user management features of the system. The service is provided by the University and State

Library Darmstadt through Base4NFDI. The main improvements through NFDI4Energy are **energy-related templates for data and software management plans**, which energy system researchers can use directly in the RDMO4Energy instance.

The **Open Energy Scenario Bundles** enable the bundling of information about scenarios, studies, models, and frameworks, all elements of crucial importance in energy system research. From a user perspective, the scenario bundles allow for the **documentation of the context of an energy research scenario**. This includes information about studies, input and output data, and the utilized models and frameworks. From a technical perspective, information on models, scenarios, and utilized data is stored in the Open Energy Knowledge Graph, which can be searched through the provided interface or through a SPARQL endpoint. The main improvement through NFDI4Energy is the **adoption of the new Open Energy Knowledge Graph**, including an improved knowledge graph design and SHACL validation as well as an updated frontend.

The **Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)** makes scientific work findable and comparable [51]. Its development and operation is funded through the institutional mission of the TIB. From a user perspective, the ORKG allows researchers to create **detailed semantic descriptions of research papers**. These descriptions enable scientific literature comparisons and make research content more accessible, allowing for efficient analysis of research works and better discovery of related contributions. From a technical perspective, the ORKG uses a graph data model to represent semantic statements as graphs using nodes and edges. The backend-infrastructure supports functionalities like finding related contributions and facilitating literature reviews. Provenance information is captured as metadata, providing transparency about when and by whom statements were created. The main improvement through NFDI4Energy is the creation of the **Energy System Research Observatory**.

The **Leibniz Data Manager (LDM)** federates RDM [52–54]. From a user perspective, the LDM provides researchers with the **ability to upload and download datasets along with their associated metadata**. Available datasets and files can be easily viewed, including support for various data types like CSV, CAD, and image files. Additionally, tabular data can be explored and compared with data from other datasets using simple online plots, and Jupyter notebooks can be run directly within the platform. From a technical perspective, the LDM utilizes the **Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN)** and knowledge graphs. This enables the storage of data directly on the server, while also allowing for redirection to datasets hosted on external platforms, where only the corresponding metadata is stored locally on the server. Furthermore, the metadata of datasets in the LDM is linked to the ORKG. The main improvements through NFDI4Energy are setting up a specific **NFDI4Energy instance, answering natural language questions over the federation of open research knowledge graphs** like

the LDM knowledge graph and the ORKG, the **comparison of multiple datasets** in tabular format through online plots, and the integration of IAM4NFDI and the TIB Terminology Service.

The **Open Energy Database** is a service to store energy research data and make it FAIR. From a user perspective, the Open Energy Database offers **upload and download functions for energy-related data, enabling access to datasets with open licenses**. It uses OEMetadata as a metadata schema and provides a user interface for entering and editing metadata. From a technical perspective, the Open Energy Database provides RESTful APIs for accessing and uploading data and metadata and supports SPARQL queries. The main improvements through NFDI4Energy are the **extension of the training material for the service** as well as the **integration of IAM4NFDI** and the updated OEMetadata standard 2.0.

The **Open Energy Databus** allows users to **link energy data over their lifecycles**. From a user perspective, it allows to access linked open metadata via linked data or SPARQL queries. Together with explicit support for decentralized and heterogeneous file storage systems, it enables the integration of various data sources from the energy domain in a unified and highly interoperable way. From a technical perspective, the Open Energy Databus is a metadata knowledge graph describing files of different formats from the energy domain, including integrity measures. The main improvements through NFDI4Energy are an **improved user interface, modular multi-domain metadata modules** and **improved account management**, which were all financed through a Flex Project.

Besides the services in operation, we also **develop** the following **additional services**:

The **Anonymization4Energy** service will enable researchers to **anonymize sensitive energy data**, in order to simplify the usage of data from **industry**. From a user perspective, the service enables secure data sharing and collaboration while protecting proprietary and personal information and preventing the exposure of raw data [55]. Therefore, the service should lower the transaction costs of data sharing, especially for industry collaborations. From a technical perspective, the service applies techniques such as k-anonymity and aggregation, and then evaluates the anonymized output for information loss and reidentification risk.

The **Competence4Energy** service will allow its users to **find potential research partners** based on their competencies, profiles, and location. From a technical perspective, the service is built using an Angular-based frontend framework and a PostgreSQL database backend. The main achievement of NFDI4Energy is the development and long-term provision of a usable service based on a prototype from a former project (**Zukunftslabor Energie**) and the integration of IAM4NFDI for authentication.

The **Simulation as a Service Hub** (SimaaS Hub) will support **energy system simulation** [56] and significantly lower the barriers to using simulation-based models in energy system research. From a user perspective, the SimaaS Hub will offer a web portal for energy domain co-simulations. It will offer best-practice guidance, introduce the mosaik [57], VILLASframework [58], and

DaceDS [59] frameworks, and let users run predefined or custom scenarios. Results are visualized online and downloadable. A tool-and-model registry will support resource discovery. From a technical perspective, the SimaaS Hub will link co-simulation frameworks via standardized APIs. The hub will automatically orchestrate simulation tasks and provide scalable, interoperable, and reproducible research workflows (mockup in [56]).

The **Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software** (SMECS) is an early-state service, which supports researchers in the **creation of metadata for their research software** [60]. From a user perspective, SMECS allows the extraction of existing research software metadata and their user-friendly editing. It allows researchers to efficiently create high-quality metadata without reentering information already available elsewhere. From a technical perspective, SMECS facilitates the extraction of research software metadata from GitHub and GitLab repositories. SMECS supports the use of CodeMeta and ERSmeta, and thus is tailored to our community. The curated metadata can be exported as JSON, ensuring integration with other tools and enhancing the discoverability, reuse, and impact of research software. In future development, we aim to integrate the TIB Terminology Service.

2.5 Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints

Our consortium has, since its acceptance for funding, thoroughly engaged with both the academic and political contexts in which our community operates. Our aim as NFDI4Energy is to provide services that promote research excellence through good ERDM. Consequently, continuous and agile adaptation to evolving conditions is absolutely imperative.

The **political landscape** has changed since the beginning of our initiative. The discussions on **digital sovereignty for Europe**, driven by recent political developments (especially in the US), do not affect only industry, but application-oriented research as well. As a consequence, federated concepts for data storage as well as security and **resilience measures** are needed. This influences both our service development and our service requirements. Additionally, our activities include a case study with a large German energy utility assessing data potentials for research when complying with the **EU Data Act**. On a national level, we engage in discussions regarding data exchange and data processing in institutions, like the discussions regarding the German **Dateninstitut** and its energy use case (see [BMDS paper regarding the development of the Dateninstitut](#)), to drive the connection of industry, society, and research within this context.

Political changes also affect **research policy**. Of utmost importance are the decisions to drive **Germany's AI capabilities**. We engage in several activities within this context and expect further effects on our service portfolio strategy. To give examples, we engage in activities regarding **the AI-GIGA factory** (e.g., with our co-spokesperson Antonello Monti being responsible for the energy activities in JUPITER AI Factory (JAIF)) and new research proposals from our co-applicant

institutions regarding generative artificial intelligence (AI) developments for EOSC. We see tremendous synergies between our work and these developments regarding **data curation and preparation for AI services** for energy system research. Within this context, we follow discussions regarding European legislation, like the **EU AI Act**.

Data competencies are becoming more relevant in general as well as specifically in research. Research policy has given many incentives in recent years to push efforts in this direction. Many of our co-spokespersons engage in RDM activities at their universities.

Meanwhile, the [different Landesinitiativen Forschungsdatenmanagement](#) (state's initiatives for RDM) have evolved and started to integrate their offers with the NFDI. We cooperate with many of them to yield a **consistent support offer** in close cooperation with all actors in this field.

Within the state's initiatives for RDM in Lower Saxony, we applied for a project focusing on RSE (ROSS, submitted fall 2025, not decided yet). RSE is a topic that we did not cover in our initial proposal, but that has evolved from activities within NFDI4Energy. As a result, the consortium started to build up the topic of energy RSE with participation in deRSE conferences through multiple contributions in 2024 and 2025 [46, 61–67], participation within the Working Group RSE of the Section Common Infrastructures [68], and a presentation of a poster on “Building a RSE Community in Energy Research” at CoRDI 2025 [69]. In addition, we participated in the proposal of `nfdi.software` for the initialization phase, and included domain-specific templates for software management plans in RDMO4Energy [70].

3 Additional Aspects

3.1 Equal opportunities

Equal opportunities and diversity are essential foundations of excellent science. We actively implement these measures in both structure and practice, although no specific funding was allocated for dedicated diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) measures in the funding scheme. The consortium is interdisciplinary by design and continues to expand in thematic and institutional diversity. All participating institutions follow equal opportunity policies and non-discriminatory hiring practices, resulting in diverse teams that include international researchers.

We see a **gender ratio** within NFDI4Energy that is slightly over 30% female researchers, exceeding the typical average in computer science. While the consortium does not only include computer science, the majority of researchers have backgrounds stemming from engineering, with a typically lower female:male ratio. Some specific activities have been offered, e.g., an online women's pre-networking event at the first NFDI4Energy Conference. To promote equal participation for persons with care duties and to reduce carbon emissions, every second task area meeting and most coordination sessions are held online. **Early career researchers** are within the focus of our DEI activities, taking active roles in workshop and conference preparation and organization. As

an example, the highly interactive formats at our conferences foster an exchange between researchers at all career stages. Additionally, we established a timeslot for doctoral students to network at our conferences. We motivate and support early career researchers to take on leading roles within our consortium, e.g., as task area and measure leads.

English is used as the working language to foster inclusive communication, and measures such as onboarding sessions support an inclusive working environment. We also adopted the [NFDI code of conduct](#) for the work in our consortium and for the NFDI4Energy Conferences, as a basis for respectful cooperation.

Our commitment to diversity extends beyond team composition and has an **influence on our research design**. For example, the requirements analysis integrated multiple disciplines and stakeholder perspectives [2], while focus groups and interviews on energy transition acceptance are designed to ensure regional and demographic diversity. Moreover, the outcomes of NFDI4Energy are intended for use by researchers, industry, and society.

To ensure **broad accessibility**, we have relaunched our website based on stakeholder needs, with accessibility as a guiding principle.

Through these measures, we actively contribute to a research culture that values diversity, enables participation, and strengthens the societal relevance of its work.

3.2 Reflections and comments

These first years of NFDI4Energy have strengthened our hypothesis that there is a significant demand in energy research for reusable quality-assured annotated data from various sources, like research, public administration, and industry [71, 72]. Besides this need for data, support for ERDM beyond purely technical solutions enables the energy system research community to implement good RDM and thus foster excellent research. While training is an important aspect to address this need, we did not put enough emphasis on this aspect in our funding proposal. Therefore, we have worked on and succeeded in retrieving funding to **develop appropriate training material**, e.g., with [TEN.efzn Academy](#) and our first [self-learning course](#) based on EFZN funding. We will also integrate the first outcomes of NFDI4Energy into [energy-specific training courses](#) offered by HMC. Similarly, we did not plan a helpdesk for this funding phase of NFDI4Energy. Nevertheless, we established a preliminary [helpdesk](#) and are in discussions on how to sustainably staff it and establish links to the helpdesks of other NFDI consortia.

As a **consortium of the third funding round**, we benefit from the experiences of earlier consortia. Thus, we have been able to quickly adapt our management and operating mode. NFDI as a whole has therefore already helped substantially to push the NFDI4Energy work forward, e.g., through the collaboration in the NFDI sections and the use of the emerging base services.

Regarding the NFDI association, there is a need for a structural and procedural evolution to ensure the long-term success of NFDI. We engage in all activities to define these structures in a

consortia-driven bottom-up process. This should be combined with a central perspective from research funding.

As a consortium more familiar with research projects and less familiar with infrastructure service and maintenance, we underestimated the effort to manage all tasks involved in an NFDI consortium. Thus, we started with an **understaffed coordination office**. We were able to overcome this problem to some extent, e.g., using in-kind contributions.

Writing this progress report is a good occasion to reflect on the potential risks that were identified for the first funding phase of NFDI4Energy. As of now, none of the risks have materialized, while one risk needs closer attention in the upcoming phase, and a new risk has arisen:

- We had identified the risk that there might be a **low acceptance of FAIRification principles within the energy-related industry**. We are sure that this risk has to be monitored, and have started to develop specific services for industry stakeholders (e.g., Anonymization4Energy). We will take an **active role beyond already-planned activities**. First steps have been taken through active involvement in the Future Energy Lab activities lead by the German Energy Agency (Deutsch Energie-Agentur, dena), resulting in a [joint paper with BMDS](#). Additionally, a pilot with industry partners to evaluate and improve their data processes is under discussion.
- A **new risk** has been identified, resulting from the diverse research landscape in Germany: currently, many services (including base services) within the NFDI can be used only with university affiliations, while not all research institutes have access. We will actively engage in solving this issue in the near future.

Appendix

1 List of outputs produced by the consortium

Table 2 Overview of the reported outputs sorted by FaBiO classes

FaBiO class	Number
abstract	31
book chapter	2
conference poster	18
conference/proceedings paper	12
deliverable	36
journal article	12
presentation	26
other	2
Total	139

1.1 Abstracts

Chaianong, A., Hoffart, F. M., Kerker, N., Lilliestam, J., & Weko, S. (2024, February 14). Datasets and time series for energy policy research and modelling. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10656917>

Chaianong, A., Weko, S., Milioritsas, P. M. I., & Lilliestam, J. (2025, June 15). Targets as drivers of future progress or reflections of past action? Energy Solutions for a Sustainable and Inclusive Future. <https://iaee.org/proceedings/article/19081>

Davidson, H., Chaianong, A., Qussous, R., Milioritsas, I., Lilliestam, J., & Schäfer, M. (2025, March 26). Integration of regulatory constraints from a policy database into the energy system modeling tool atlite. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118167>

Ferenz, S., Ahrens, A., Heiken, J., Jandrich, A., Nieße, A., & Seitz, N. (2024, February 8). Open Training for Research Data Management in the Energy Domain. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10635422>

Ferenz, S., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025, March 10). Towards a Metadata Scheme for Energy Research Software. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14998538>

Fritz, P., Seiwert, C., & Weinhardt, C. (2025, March 24). Bridging the gap between Industry and Academia—An Overview of Data Sharing Possibilities. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17943055>

Frost, E., Schäfer, M., Schmurr, P., Nieße, A., & Weidlich, A. (2025, March 27). Enhancing Research Data Management through Use Cases in Energy Research. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15097399>

Grether, R. L., Schäfer, M., Qussous, R., Hoffart, F. M., Kerker, N., Speck, C., Lilliestam, J., Weinhardt, C., & Weidlich, A. (2024, February 20). Representation of societal and political factors in long-term energy system scenarios. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849101>

- Kerker, N., Hoffart, F. M., Schäfer, M., Lilliestam, J., & Speck, C. (2024, March 26). Building Bridges: An Interdisciplinary (Energy) Research Framework. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10875243>
- Lu, L., & Wein, A. (2025, March 13). Unveiling Openness in Energy Research: A Bibliometric Analysis Focusing on Open Access and Data Sharing Practices. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15017463>
- Manzek, L., Niemann, L., Steinert, A., Wagner, H., Werth, O., Penaherrera, F., & Lier, S. K. (2025, February 3). Enhancing Software Sustainability: Transferring Open-Science Solutions from ZLE to NFDI4Energy. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14792601>
- Pan, Z., Gürses-Tran, G., Speck, C., Jaquart, P., Niebisch, M., & Monti, A. (2023). Transparency and Involvement of the Energy-Related Industry in a Data Sharing Platform. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.270>
- Peters, F. N., Burghardt, C., Weidlich, A., & Schäfer, M. (2025, March 18). Sectoral Demand Modeling in German Long-Term Energy Scenarios. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045628>
- Rohde, P. D., Iglesias, E., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024, March 4). FedORKG: Accessing Federations of Open Research Knowledge Graphs. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776280>
- Rohde, P. D., Sakor, A., Brunet, M., Iglesias, E., Bechara, M., Arndt, S., Begoin, M., Kraft, A., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024, March 4). The Leibniz Data Manager: Supporting Researchers in the Lifecycle of Research Data. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776314>
- Schäfer, M., Buckley, T., & Weidlich, A. (2025, March 14). Where do Germany's electricity imports come from? A tale of energy system data availability and interpretation. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15025563>
- Schäfer, M., Qussous, R., Hülk, L., Lilliestam, J., & Weidlich, A. (2023). NFDI4Energy Case-Study: Comparative Analysis and Visualisation of Long-Term Energy System Scenarios. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.294>
- Schwarz, J. S., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwerth, C., Qussous, R., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., & Weidlich, A. (2025, March 20). Towards an ontology for co-simulation scenarios of energy systems. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15061653>
- Schwarz, J. S., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwerth, C., Qussous, R., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., Weidlich, A., & Hülk, L. (2025, August 4). Developing an ontology for co-simulation scenarios of energy systems. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736210>
- Sedighi, F., Pan, Z., & Monti, A. (2024, April 23). Analysis of Data Substitution Requirements and Techniques in Energy Research. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11046006>
- Seiwerth, C., Niebisch, M., & German, R. (2024, February 15). Towards a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658172>

Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes Grau, L., German, R., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., & Nieße, A. (2025, August 4). Developing a Workflow for Using Simulation in Research. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736050>

Speck, C., Herrmann, S., Pan, Z., Sedighi, F., Seiwerth, C., Niebisch, M., & Weinhardt, C. (2024, February 14). Drivers and Challenges of Open Data from an Energy Industry Perspective. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658531>

Speck, C., Jaquart, P., Weinhardt, C., Lilliestam, J., Schäfer, M., Weidlich, A., Zilles, J., & Kerker, N. (2023). Transparency and Involvement of Society and Policy in a Data Sharing Platform. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.327>

Steinert, A., Nieße, A., & Werth, O. (2024, February 15). Doing What is the Best: Best Practices in Energy Research A Structured Literature Review. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666998>

Stucky, K.-U., Koubaa, M. A., Liu, N., Schmidt, A., Süß, W., & Hagenmeyer, V. (2024, February 4). Towards a Conception and the Implementation of FAIR Data Management Tools for the Energy Domain. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10614814>

Thiery, F., Flemisch, B., Hetényi, B., Seiwerth, C., Baum, R., Bernoth, J., Ferez, S., Linxweiler, J., Reinhardt, M., & Schubert, L. (2025, August 4). RSE 4 Research Data Infrastructures—The Role of Research Software Engineers in creating FAIR Data with FAIR4RS Code. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736042>

Wein, A., Reinkensmeier, J., Weidlich, A., Lilliestam, J., Hagenmeyer, V., Richter, M., Auer, S., Nieße, A., & Lehnhoff, S. (2023). FAIR Data for Energy System Research: An Overview of NFDI4Energy Task Area 4. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.364>

Weko, S., Chaianong, A., Lilliestam, J., Milioritsas, I., & Bersalli, G. (2025, March 25). Which Policy Instruments Do Governments Use, and Which Ones Do Researchers Study? 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17942895>

Werth, O., Ferez, S., Niese, A., German, R., Huelck, L., Weinhardt, C., & Vogel, B. (2023). Current Insights From Task Area 1 in NFDI4Energy: Building and Serving the Energy Research Community. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.350>

Wiese, F., Zell-Ziegler, C., Burghardt, C., Kloos, Y., & Schäfer, M. (2024, February 15). Benchmarking sufficiency assumptions: Comparison of energy and climate scenarios and build-up of a sufficiency potential database. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666308>

1.2 Book chapters

Kamsamrong, J., Widl, E., Schwarz, J. S., Heussen, K., Raussi, P., Arnold, G., De Paola, A., Feng, Z., Werth, O., Pham, M. C., & Tran, Q. T. (2025). Enhanced Validation Methods and Benchmark. In T. I. Strasser, M. Calin, & L. E. Ramos Perez (Eds.), European Guide to Smart Energy System Testing: The ERIGrid 2.0 Approach for Evaluating Complex Smart Energy System Configurations (pp. 23–33). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-99451-7_3

Lombardi, F., Süsser, D., Wiese, F., Lilliestam, J., & Pfenninger, S. (2025). Open Models Are Not Enough. Advancing Energy System Modelling Towards Practical Usefulness. In R. M. Erd-

beer, V. Hagenmeyer, & K. Stierstorfer (Eds.), *Modelling the Energy Transition: Cultures, Visions, Narratives* (pp. 173–195). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-69031-0_9.

1.3 Conference posters

Ferenz, S., Frost, E., Schrage, R., Wolgast, T., Werth, O., Beyers, I., & Nieße, A. (2023, March 26). Poster: Towards Guidelines for Engineering of Energy Research Software. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15357363>

Frost, E., Ferenz, S., & Nieße, A. (2025, March 27). Research Data Management Course for Energy Research. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15097256>

Gao, Y., Pan, Z., Foroogh, S., & Monti, A. (2025, August 4). Collaborative Data Anonymization Process. Zenodo. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735882>

Hoffart, F. M., Kerker, N., & Werth, O. (2024, March 4). An Energy Data Service Platform for Whom? Understanding the Needs of the Energy Research Community. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10778102>

Kotthoff, F., & Hülk, L. (2025, April 1). From Software to Service: Advancing open-mastr. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119904>

Muhammad, A., & Engel, F. (2025a, March 7). Query Term Recommendation Using Domain-Specific Ontologies and Sentence Transformers. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988979>

Muhammad, A., & Engel, F. (2025b, August 4). An Ontology-Based Text Annotation Tool for NFDI4Energy. Zenodo. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735787>

Pan, Z., Gao, Y., Foroogh, S., Fritz, P., Seiwerth, C., Halikulov, N., Wirtz, N., & Monti, A. (2025, August 4). Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data. Zenodo. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735836>

Qussous, R., Schwarz, J. S., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwerth, C., Ferenz, S., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., & Weidlich, A. (2025, August 4). Refining Metadata for Energy Simulation Software. Zenodo. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736271>

Rohde, P. D., & Vidal, M.-E. (2025, March 26). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025—Service Poster—Leibniz Data Manager (LDM). 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221686>

Schmurr, P., Steinert, A., Hülk, L., Werth, O., Wein, A., & Seiwerth, C. (2025, August 4). Enhancing Requirements Engineering Through Transparent Collection and Monitoring—A Metadata Schema and GitHub Repository Blueprint for a Requirement Collection Process. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16735998>

Schwarz, J. S. (2025, March 25). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025—Service Poster—Mosaik-as-a-service. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15592533>

Seiwerth, C., & Ferenz, S. (2025, September 11). Building a RSE Community in Energy Research. Zenodo. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100689>

Seiwerth, C., Halikulov, N., & German, R. (2025, March 21). Extending a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064826>

Seiwerth, C., Niebisch, M., Ferez, S., & German, R. (2024, March 5). Research Software Engineering in the Energy Domain as Part of NFDI4Energy. deRSE24 - Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany (deRSE24). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17710540>

Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes Grau, L., German, R., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., & Nieße, A. (2025, March 21). Towards a Simulation-as-a-Service Hub for the Energy Domain. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15065996>

Seiwerth, C., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Schwarz, J. S., Liu, N., Schmurr, P., Qussous, R., Pan, Z., Ferez, S., & German, R. (2025, February 25). From Start to Finish- The Ideal Process of Using Simulation Software in Energy Research Projects. deRSE 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17710286>

Steinert, A., & Brandt, T. (2025, November 26). Using TimescaleDB and Apache Superset to support Co-Simulation Data Exploration. deRSE24 - Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany (deRSE24).

1.4 Conference proceedings

Bonilla, J., Thonig, R., Carballo, J. A., Lilliestam, J., Alarcón-Padilla, D. C., & Zarza, E. (2024). CSP Data: A Data Discovery Web Application of Commercial CSP Plants. SolarPACES Conference Proceedings, 2. <https://doi.org/10.52825/solarpaces.v2i.811>

Ferez, S., Frost, E., Schrage, R., Wolgast, T., Beyers, I., Karras, O., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025). Ten Recommendations for Engineering Research Software in Energy Research. Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Future and Sustainable Energy Systems, E-Energy '25, 446–459. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3679240.3734606>

Ferez, S., Jafarbigloo, A., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025). SMECS: A Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software. Electronic Communications of the EASST, 85. <https://doi.org/10.14279/eceasst.v85.2708>

Ferez, S., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025). Requirements for a Metadata Scheme to Enable FAIR Energy Research Software. Electronic Communications of the EASST, 83(Electronic Communications of the EASST, Vol. 83 (2025): deRSE24-Selected Contributions of the 4th Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany). <https://doi.org/10.14279/ECE-ASST.V83.2594>

Radtke, M., & Frost, E. (2025). Simulative Analysis of Multi-Agent Systems in Energy Systems: Impact of Communication Networks. 523–530. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0013241400003890>

Sakor, A., Brunet, M., Iglesias, E., Rivas, A., Rohde, P. D., Kraft, A., & Vidal, M.-E. (2025). Integrating Knowledge Graphs and Neuro-Symbolic AI: LDM Enables FAIR and Federated Research Data Management. Proceedings of the Eighteenth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, WSDM '25, 1044–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3701551.3704125>

Schäfer, M., Buckley, T., Weidlich, A., & Boerman, F. (2025). Where Do Germany's Electricity Imports Come From? 2025 21st International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM64765.2025.11050092>

Steinert, A., Ferenz, S., & Nieße, A. (2025). Choosing the Right Ontology to Describe Research Data in the Energy Domain. *SIGENERGY Energy Inform. Rev.*, 4(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3717413.3717417>

Wein, A., Bechara, M., Rohde, P. D., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024, June). Towards FAIR Data in Energy System Research: Challenges and Perspectives [Application/pdf]. 4th Workshop on Metadata and Research (objects) Management for Linked Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006474025>

Wein, A., Reinkensmeier, J., Weidlich, A., Lilliestam, J., Hagenmeyer, V., & Lehnhoff, S. (2023). NFDI4Energy Task Area 4: FAIR Data for Energy System Research. 937–944. <https://dl.gi.de/handle/20.500.12116/43026>

Wein, A., Steinert, A., Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes-Grau, L., Pan, Z., Monti, A., & Nieße, A. (2024). Developing Interoperable Ontologies for Research Data Management in the Energy Domain. Proceedings of the Joint Ontology Workshops (JOWO) - Episode X: The Tukker Zomer of Ontology, and Satellite Events Co-Located with the 14th International Conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems (FOIS 2024), CEUR Workshop Proceedings, 3882. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/emsusto-2.pdf>

Werth, O., Köhlke, J., & Nickerson, R. (2024, December 15). Beyond the Border – A Taxonomic Analysis of the Adoption of Boundary Objects in Information Systems Research. ICIS 2024 Proceedings. https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2024/it_implement/it_implement/7

1.5 Deliverables

Chaianong, A., Malhotra, P., Milioritsas, I., Weko, S., & Lilliestam, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Deliverable 2.2.2.2: Data on climate and renewable electricity targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15476344>

Chaianong, A., Milioritsas, I., Malhotra, P., Günkördü, D., Weko, S., Weiß, J., & Lilliestam, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Deliverable 2.2.1.1: Data on landscape and environmental regulation for energy production and infrastructure. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15477076>

Chaianong, A., Weko, S., Milioritsas, I., & Lilliestam, J. (2026). D6.4.5 Showcase of extended target data and analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18433560>

Förster, H., Winger, C., & Huber, J. (2026). D8.3.1 The improved Open Energy Platform. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18383631>

Frost, E. (2026a). D6.4.3.1 Comparing State-of-The-Art Approaches in Energy System Research by Using the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18313489>

Frost, E. (2026b). D6.4.7.1 Kicking off a Data Management Plan (DMP) in an Energy System Research Project. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18313513>

Frost, E., Seiwerth, C., & Halikulov, N. (2025). NFDI4Energy Deliverable 6.3.2.1 Requirements for implementation of distributed simulation for distributed energy systems. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15746158>

Kerker, N., Hoffart, F. M., Werth, O., & Großmann, M. (2024). D1.1.4.1 Platform requirements analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524617>

Kerker, N., Speck, C., Hoffart, F. M., & Pan, Z. (2024). D2.1.1.1 List and graphic overview on relevant stakeholders. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14383061>

Kotthoff, F., Steinert, A., Werth, O., Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2025). D7.7.1.1 Designing a Consortium Service Portfolio – NFDI4Energy’s Criteria and Process for Integrating Services. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17700571>

Kuhlmann, L., & Ferez, S. (2024). D7.3.7.1 Social Media Strategy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13932944>

Pan, Z., Gao, Y., Sedighi, F., Fritz, P. T., Seiwert, C., Halikulov, N., & Wirtz, N. (2025). D3.2.1.1 Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data defined and executed with industry partners. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17830664>

Peters, F. N., Muhammad, A., Engel, F., Schäfer, M., & Stappel, M. (2026). D6.4.4.1 Streamlining Long-Term Energy System Scenario Data Annotation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18352554>

Qussous, R., Seiwert, C., Schwarz, J. S., Liu, N., Schmurr, P., Pan, Z., & Ferez, S. (2025). D5.1.1.1 Define requirements for metadata schema. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542734>

Qussous, R., Seiwert, C., Schwarz, J. S., Liu, N., Schmurr, P., Pan, Z., & Ferez, S. (2026). D5.1.1.2 Energy simulation software metadata schema. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18390186>

Rohde, P. D., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024a). D4.4.1.1 Implementation of Federated Access. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652249>

Rohde, P. D., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024b). D4.4.1.2 Federated Architecture for Federated Search. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652297>

Rohde, P. D., & Vidal, M.-E. (2024c). D4.4.2.3 1st Version of the Leibniz Data Manager. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652326>

Schäfer, M., & Buckley, T. (2026). D6.4.2.1 Showcase “Electricity imports.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18236569>

Schäfer, M., Frost, E., & Schmurr, P. (2026). D6.4.1.1 Showcase description template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18352349>

Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Süß, W., & Fuentes Grau, L. (2025). NFDI4Energy Use Case M6.1 Description. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16606312>

Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Wein, A., Schwarz, J. S., Steinert, A., Qussous, R., Chaianong, A., & Hülk, L. (2025a). D4.3.1 Technical requirements for metadata in NFDI4Energy services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14937740>

Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Wein, A., Schwarz, J. S., Steinert, A., Qussous, R., Chaianong, A., & Hülk, L. (2025b). D4.3.2 List of Metadata Standards and Relevance for NFDI4Energy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549282>

Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes Grau, L., Liu, N., Pan, Z., Qussous, R., Schmurr, P., Seiwert, C., Steinert, A., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., & Weidlich, A. (2025). D5.2.1.1 Registry of relevant domain ontologies for co-simulation scenario definition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14521502>

Sedighi, F., Pan, Z., & Gao, Y. (2025). D3.3.1.1 List of required substitute data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063698>

- Seiwerth, C., Halikulov, N., & German, R. (2025). D 5.3.3.1 Extending a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268434>
- Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes Grau, L., German, R., Lehnhoff, S., Nieße, A., & Monti, A. (2025). D5.3.1.1 Requirements for the Implementation of NFDI4Energy Use Cases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699093>
- Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J. S., Fuentes Grau, L., Liu, N., Pan, Z., Qussous, R., & Schmurr, P. (2026). D5.4.6 A SMP Catalog for the Energy Research Software Engineering Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18254298>
- Speck, C., Pan, Z., Sedighi, F., Seiwerth, C., Niebisch, M., Dognini, A., & Weinhardt, C. (2025). D3.1.2.1 Design thinking workshop for industry partners. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645840>
- Speck, C., Pan, Z., & Weinhardt, C. (2025). D3.1.1.1 Network of relevant industry partners. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645627>
- Speck, C., Schulz, T., & Weinhardt, C. (2026). D2.5.1.2 Mapping Energy Data Gaps and Reuse Barriers: Evidence and Implications for NFDI4Energy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231310>
- Wein, A., Engel, F., Hülk, L., Liu, N., Muhammad, A., Peters, F., Schmurr, P., Stappel, M., Steinert, A., & Weko, S. (2026). D4.1.1.1 Overview of Metadata and Ontology Interaction with NFDI4Energy Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18255229>
- Weko, S., Bersalli, G., Chaianong, A., Lilliestam, J., & Milioritsas, I. (2026). D6.4.6 Showcase Climate and Energy Policy Ontology. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18386069>
- Weko, S., Bersalli, G., Chaianong, A., Milioritsas, I., & Lilliestam, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Deliverable D4.5.1.1 Policy ontology report & Excel spreadsheet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15583093>
- Weko, S., Malhotra, P., Chaianong, A., Milioritsas, I., & Lilliestam, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Deliverable 2.2.2.1: Data on policy support for renewable electricity and electric vehicles. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15477244>
- Werth, O., Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2026). D7.1.7.1 NFDI4Energy—Research Data Management Commitment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18347506>

1.6 Journal articles

- Barani, M., Löffler, K., Crespo del Granado, P., Moskalenko, N., Panos, E., Hoffart, F. M., Hirschhausen, C. von, Kannavou, M., Auer, H., Hainsch, K., González Grandón, T., Mathisen, S., & Tomasgard, A. (2026). European energy vision 2050 and beyond: Designing scenarios for Europe's energy transition. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 225, 116074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116074>
- Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2023). Towards Improved Findability of Energy Research Software by Introducing a Metadata-based Registry. *Ing.Grid*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.48694/inggrid.3837>
- Hasselbring, W., Druskat, S., Bernoth, J., Betker, P., Felderer, M., Ferez, S., Hermann, B., Lamprecht, A.-L., Linxweiler, J., Prat, A., Rumpe, B., Schoening-Stierand, K., & Yang, S. (2025). Multi-Dimensional Research Software Categorization. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2025.3555023>

Hoffart, F. M., D’Orazio, P., Holz, F., & Kemfert, C. (2024). Exploring the interdependence of climate, finance, energy, and geopolitics: A conceptual framework for systemic risks amidst multiple crises. *Applied Energy*, 361, 122885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122885>

Hoffart, F. M., & Holz, F. (2024). Energy asset stranding in resource-rich developing countries and the just transition—A framework to push research frontiers. *Frontiers in Environmental Economics*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/freec.2024.1273315>

Kuckertz, P., Göpfert, J., Karras, O., Neuroth, D., Schönau, J., Pueblas, R., Ferez, S., Engel, F., Pflugradt, N., Weinand, J. M., Nieße, A., Auer, S., & Stolten, D. (2024). DataDesc: A framework for creating and sharing technical metadata for research software interfaces. *Patterns*, 101064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.101064>

Maedche, A., Elshan, E., Höhle, H., Lehrer, C., Recker, J., Sunyaev, A., Sturm, B., & Werth, O. (2024). Open Science—Towards Greater Transparency and Openness in Science. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 66(4), 517–532. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-024-00858-7>

Mey, F., Lilliestam, J., Wolf, I., & Tröndle, T. (2024). Visions for our future regional electricity system: Citizen preferences in four EU countries. *iScience*, 27(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.109269>

Pan, Z., Gao, Y., Ponci, F., & Monti, A. (2023). Semi-Automatic Ontology Development Framework for Building Energy Data Management. *IEEE Access*, 11, 111991–112003. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3323335>

Weko, S. (2025). New Sites of Accumulation? Why Intangible Assets Matter for Energy Transitions. *Review of Political Economy*, 37(4), 1571–1598. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09538259.2024.2391304>

Werth, O., Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2023). Nationale Dateninfrastruktur für die interdisziplinäre Energiesystemforschung und -praxis. *Zeitschrift für Energiewirtschaft*, 47(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12398-023-0940-2>

Wiese, F., Zell-Ziegler, C., Burghardt, C., Kloos, Y., & Schäfer, M. (2024). Reducing demand: A quantitative analysis of energy service demand indicators in sufficiency-oriented scenarios. *Environmental Research Communications*, 6(12), 121003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ad966e>

1.7 Presentations

Bartenstein, A. (2025, April 3). Policy pathways: Interlinking energy policy research and energy modelling. Workshop: Sustainability Research in Economics, Law and Political Science. https://www.pol.phil.fau.de/files/2025/04/Programme_SUSworkshop_FAU_2025_04.pdf

Chaianong, A., Lilliestam, J., & Milioritsas, I. (2024, August 12). Which drives what? – A climate policy sequencing analysis. ECPR General Conference 2024. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PartnerDetails/76388>

Ferez, S., Frost, E., Schrage, R., Wolgast, T., Beyers, I., Karras, O., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025, July 16). Ten Recommendations for Engineering Research Software in Energy Research. *E-Energy '25*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15962412>

Ferez, S., Frost, E., Schrage, R., Wolgast, T., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025, March 4). Towards Guidelines for Engineering of Energy Research Software. *deRSE 2025*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968117>

- Ferez, S., Jafarbigloo, A., Werth, O., & Nieße, A. (2025, March 4). SMECS: A Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software. deRSE 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968049>
- Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2025a, March 4). Towards Services to Enable FAIR Research Software in a Typical Research Project Cycle. deRSE 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968144>
- Ferez, S., & Nieße, A. (2025b, November 26). Requirements for Metadata of Energy Research Software. deRSE24 - Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany (deRSE24). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17722447>
- Lilliestam, J. (2025, August 26). Modern Climate Policy. ECPR General Conference 2025. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/79877>
- Lilliestam, J., Chaianong, A., Malhotra, P., Milioritsas, I., & Weko, S. (2025, June 15). Targets as Drivers of Future Progress or Reflections of Past Action? ECPR General Conference 2025. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/79824>
- Lilliestam, J., Chaianong, Aksornchan, Weko, Silvia, & Milioritsas, P. M. I. (2025, June 15). Targets as drivers of future progress or reflections of past action? Accelerating climate action: Examining the role of the state in emission scenarios and pathways. <https://www.sv.uio.no/isv/english/research/projects/accelz/events/closed-workshop-in-paris-may-26th-and-27th-2025-/closed-workshop-in-paris-may-26th-and-27th-2025-.html>
- Lombardi, F., Süsler, D., Wiese, F., Lilliestam, J., Bock, F., & Pfenninger-Lee, S. (2024, February 20). Open assumptions are necessary in energy system modelling. First annual conference NFDI4Energy. <https://nfdi4energy.uol.de/community-and-updates/1st-nfdi4energy-conference-2024/>
- Milioritsas, I. (2024, June 12). How can we evaluate the policy mix effectiveness? – A systematic literature review – What Works. What Works Climate Solutions Summit,. <https://what-worksclimate.solutions/presentation/how-can-we-evaluate-the-policy-mix-effectiveness-a-systematic-literature-review/>
- Milioritsas, I., Chaianong, A., & Lilliestam, J. (2024, August 12). How can we evaluate the policy mix effectiveness? – A systematic literature review. ECPR General Conference 2024. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/76266>
- Milioritsas, I., Chaianong, A., & Lilliestam, J. (2025, August 26). Policy Mix Effectiveness for Energy System Transformations: An Evidence-Based Approach. ECPR General Conference 2025. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/81366>
- Qussous, R., Seiwert, C., Schwarz, J. S., Schmurr, P., & Liu, N. (2025, March 25). Refining Metadata for Energy Simulation Software: Workshop Materials from NFDI4Energy Conference 2025. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235370>
- Schmidt, A., Koubaa, M. A., Liu, N., Stucky, K.-U., & Süß, W. (2024, April 8). Metadata Extraction from a Huge Time Series Database. Zenodo. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://zenodo.org/records/10943975>
- Stappel, M., Wein, A., & Hülk, L. (2025, March 25). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025 - Workshop 3: Introduction of the OEO Foundry for Interoperable Ontologies in NFDI4Energy and the Energy Domain. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15170830>
- Thiery, F., Flemisch, B., Bernoth, J., Seiwert, C., Linxweiler, J., & Söhn, L. (2025, February 27). How to improve the visibility and added value of RSE(s) in NFDI. In Squirrel Papers. Squirrel Papers, Zenodo. deRSE 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14976366>

Weko, S. (2024a, April 3). New sites of accumulation? Why intangible assets matter for the energy transition. International Studies Association (ISA) 2024 General Conference. <https://www.isanet.org/Conferences/ISA2024/Program>

Weko, S. (2024b, September 27). New sites of accumulation? Why intangible assets matter for energy transitions. Politik in der Polykrise. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09538259.2024.2391304>

Weko, S. (2025a, January 15). From Big Oil to Big Tech: How energy transitions are changing infrastructure politics. Institutskolloquium IfP. <https://uni-tuebingen.de/fakultaeten/wirtschafts-und-sozialwissenschaftliche-fakultaet/faecher/fachbereich-sozialwissenschaften/politikwissenschaft/newsfullview-politikwissenschaft/article/institutskolloquium-ifp-150125-from-big-oil-to-big-tech-how-energy-transitions-are-changing-infrastructure-politics/>

Weko, S. (2025b, April 22). Europe's Geoeconomic Turn in Global Perspective. Europe and the geoeconomic challenge. <https://www.villavigoni.eu/de/event/europe-and-the-geoeconomic-challenge/>

Weko, S. (2025c, August 26). Power Struggles: AI, Energy Actors, and Big Tech's Digital Infrastructure. ECPR General Conference 2025. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/79604>

Weko, S., Chaianong, A., Lilliestam, J., Milioritsas, I., & Bersalli, G. (2025, April 3). Climate Policy in Practice: Which instruments do governments use, and which ones do researchers study? Workshop: Sustainability Research in Economics, Law and Political Science. https://www.pol.phil.fau.de/files/2025/04/Programme_SUSworkshop_FAU_2025_04.pdf

Weko, S., & Lilliestam, J. (2024, August 12). Does cross-sectoral policy sequencing exist? ECPR General Conference 2024. <https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/75712>

Weko, Silvia. (2025, March 27). Power Struggles: AI, energy actors, and Big Tech's digital infrastructure. Workshop: Transnational Infrastructures in Geoeconomic Competition Invited Talk 2025. <https://uni-tuebingen.de/universitaet/profil/freunde-und-foerderer/universitaetsbund/mitwirken/ihr-engagement-kommt-an/newsfullview-engagement/article/transnational-infrastructures-in-geoeconomic-competition/>

1.8 Other

Bechara, M. (2024). Understanding the Requirements of Data Spaces in the Energy Sector [Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover]. <https://doi.org/10.15488/16547>

Weko, S. (2025, June 4). Von Big Oil zu Big Tech: Die Ausweitung der Tech-Konzernmacht auf den Energiesektor. Rebalance Now. <https://rebalance-now.de/von-big-oil-zu-big-tech/>

2 Bibliography

1. Werth, O., Ferez, S., Nieße, A.: D7.1.7.1 NFDI4Energy - Research Data Management Commitment. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18347506>.
2. Kerker, N., Hoffart, F.M., Werth, O., Großmann, M.: D1.1.4.1 Platform requirements analysis. Zenodo (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524617>.
3. Speck, C., Pan, Z., Sedighi, F., Seiwert, C., Niebisch, M., Dognini, A., Weinhardt, C.: D3.1.2.1 Design thinking workshop for industry partners. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645840>.

4. Ferenz, S., Miller, B., Busse, C., Demandt, É., Eberl, F., Ebert, B., Fluck, J., Förstner, K.U., Goedicke, M., Hennig, C., Jagusch, G.W., Jansen, L., Keller, C., Krieger, U., Rettberg, N., Schrade, T., Seegert, J., von Suchodoletz, D., Trippel, T., Weidtkamp-Peters, S.: Arbeitsplan 2025 der Taskforce Governance and Sustainability (TFGS) - Schritte zur Weiterentwicklung unserer NFDI. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181340>.
5. Eberl, F., Jansen, L., Miller, B., Amelung, L., Danabalan, R., Demandt, É., Deschler, K., Eggert, M., Engel, J., Espinoza, S., Ferenz, S., Fritzsche, F., Goedicke, M., Götz, B., Hennig, C., Hofmann, A., Hoffmann, C., Hunold, J., Idda, T., Jojo, T., Jutz, R., Krieger, U., Meister, M., Nüst, D., Pittroff, S., Sauerland, K., Schmidt, C., Schneide, C., Schwarz, A., Schwetje, T., Seegert, J., Trippel, T.: Collaborative work in NFDI. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880071>.
6. Koepler, O., Schrade, T., Neumann, S., Stotzka, R., Wiljes, C., Blümel, I., Bracht, C., Hamann, T., Arndt, S., Hunold, J.: Sektionskonzept Meta(daten), Terminologien und Provenienz zur Einrichtung einer Sektion im Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5619089>.
7. Castro, L.J., Ferenz, S., Fuhrmans, M., Göpfert, J., Iglezakis, D., Karras, O., Struck, A.: "Research Software Metadata" - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata). Zenodo (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246218>.
8. Castro, L.J., Mathiak, B., Nieße, A.: Connected Open Source Software - ConnOSS - Proposal. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15616384>.
9. Huber, S.: Third General Assembly of int:net, <https://intnet.eu/news/68-third-general-assembly-of-int-net>, last accessed 2025/11/11.
10. Heussen, K., Gehrke, O.: Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop 2024, <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14162093>, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162093>.
11. Barani, M., Löffler, K., Crespo del Granado, P., Moskalenko, N., Panos, E., Hoffart, F.M., Hirschhausen, C. von, Kannavou, M., Auer, H., Hainsch, K., González Grandón, T., Mathisen, S., Tomasgard, A.: European energy vision 2050 and beyond: Designing scenarios for Europe's energy transition. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 225, 116074 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116074>.
12. Frost, E.: Robustness of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems: Incidents, <https://orkg.org/comparisons/R753752>. <https://doi.org/10.48366/R753752>.
13. Frost, E.: D6.4.3.1 Comparing State-of-The-Art Approaches in Energy System Research by Using the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG). Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18313489>.
14. Creating Comparisons for Energy System Research Using the Open Research Knowledge Graph. (2025). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q-jOXWYvUtQ>.

15. Peters, F.N., Muhammad, A., Engel, F., Schäfer, M., Stappel, M.: D6.4.4.1 Streamlining Long-Term Energy System Scenario Data Annotation. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18352554>.
16. Frost, E.: D6.4.7.1 Kicking off a Data Management Plan (DMP) in an Energy System Research Project. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18313513>.
17. Chaianong, A., Weko, S., Milioritsas, I., Lilliestam, J.: D6.4.5 Showcase of extended target data and analysis. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18433560>.
18. Schäfer, M., Speck, C.: Energie.Daten.Kommunikation - Schnittstellen zwischen Energiesystemforschung und Journalismus. SciCAR 2025. (2025).
19. Pan, Z., Gao, Y., Foroogh, S., Fritz, P., Seiwert, C., Halikulov, N., Wirtz, N., Monti, A.: Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735836>.
20. Grether, R.L., Schäfer, M., Qussous, R., Hoffart, F.M., Kerker, N., Speck, C., Lilliestam, J., Weinhardt, C., Weidlich, A.: Representation of societal and political factors in long-term energy system scenarios. Presented at the 1. NFDI4Energy Conference February 20 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849101>.
21. Peters, F.N., Burghardt, C., Weidlich, A., Schäfer, M.: Sectoral Demand Modeling in German Long-Term Energy Scenarios. Presented at the 2. NFDI4Energy Conference March 18 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045628>.
22. Wiese, F., Zell-Ziegler, C., Burghardt, C., Kloos, Y., Schäfer, M.: Reducing demand: a quantitative analysis of energy service demand indicators in sufficiency-oriented scenarios. Environ. Res. Commun. 6, 121003 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ad966e>.
23. Zell-Ziegler, C., Burghardt, C., Dünzen, K., Schöpf, D., Kurwan, J., Best, B., Schäfer, M., Wiese, F.: Energy and GHG saving potentials of sufficiency measures -- a synthesis for Germany, <http://arxiv.org/abs/2512.15359>, (2025). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.15359>.
24. Davidson, H., Chaianong, A., Qussous, R., Milioritsas, I., Lilliestam, J., Schäfer, M.: Integration of regulatory constraints from a policy database into the energy system modeling tool atlite. Presented at the 2. NFDI4Energy Conference March 26 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118167>.
25. Wierling, A., Schwanitz, V.J., Altinci, S., Bałazińska, M., Barber, M.J., Biresselioglu, M.E., Burger-Scheidlin, C., Celino, M., Demir, M.H., Dennis, R., Dintzner, N., el Gammal, A., Fernández-Peruchena, C.M., Gilcrease, W., Gładysz, P., Hoyer-Klick, C., Joshi, K., Kruczek, M., Lacroix, D., Markowska, M., Mayo-García, R., Morrison, R., Paier, M., Peronato, G., Ramakrishnan, M., Reid, J., Sciuillo, A., Solak, B., Suna, D., Süß, W., Unger, A., Fernandez Vanoni, M.L., Vasiljevic, N.: FAIR Metadata Standards for Low Carbon Energy Research—

- A Review of Practices and How to Advance. *Energies*. 14, 6692 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en14206692>.
26. Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Wein, A., Schwarz, J.S., Steinert, A., Qussous, R., Chaianong, A., Hülk, L.: D4.3.2 List of Metadata Standards and Relevance for NFDI4Energy. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549282>.
 27. Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Wein, A., Schwarz, J.S., Steinert, A., Qussous, R., Chaianong, A., Hülk, L.: D4.3.1 Technical requirements for metadata in NFDI4Energy services. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14937740>.
 28. Henzen, C., Neidiger, C., Söding, E., Trippel, T.: Report on the first NFDI Metadata Workshop. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17043517>.
 29. Hülk, L., Huber, J., Hofmann, C., Muschner, C.: Open Energy Family - Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata), <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata>, (2025).
 30. Ferez, S.: ERSmeta, <https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/ERSmeta>, (2025).
 31. Ferez, S., Werth, O., Nieße, A.: Towards a Metadata Schema for Energy Research Software, <http://arxiv.org/abs/2601.09456>, (2026). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2601.09456>.
 32. Kuckertz, P., Göpfert, J., Karras, O., Neuroth, D., Schönau, J., Pueblas, R., Ferez, S., Engel, F., Pflugradt, N., Weinand, J.M., Nieße, A., Auer, S., Stolten, D.: DataDesc: A framework for creating and sharing technical metadata for research software interfaces. *Patterns*. 101064 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.101064>.
 33. Booshehri, M., Emele, L., Flügel, S., Förster, H., Frey, J., Frey, U., Glauer, M., Hastings, J., Hofmann, C., Hoyer-Klick, C., Hülk, L., Kleinau, A., Knosala, K., Kotzur, L., Kuckertz, P., Mossakowski, T., Muschner, C., Neuhaus, F., Pehl, M., Robinius, M., Sehn, V., Stappel, M.: Introducing the Open Energy Ontology: Enhancing data interpretation and interfacing in energy systems analysis. *Energy AI*. 5, 100074 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2021.100074>.
 34. Wein, A., Steinert, A., Schwarz, J.S., Fuentes-Grau, L., Pan, Z., Monti, A., Nieße, A.: Developing Interoperable Ontologies for Research Data Management in the Energy Domain. In: Proceedings of the Joint Ontology Workshops (JOWO) - Episode X: The Tukker Zomer of Ontology, and satellite events co-located with the 14th International Conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems (FOIS 2024). , Enschede, The Netherlands (2024).
 35. Wein, A., Reinkensmeier, J., Weidlich, A., Lilliestam, J., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S.: NFDI4Energy Task Area 4: FAIR Data for Energy System Research. Presented at the INFORMATIK 2023 - Designing Futures: Zukünfte gestalten September 26 (2023).
 36. Wein, A., Reinkensmeier, J., Weidlich, A., Lilliestam, J., Hagenmeyer, V., Richter, M., Auer, S., Nieße, A., Lehnhoff, S.: FAIR Data for Energy System Research: An Overview of NFDI4Energy Task Area 4. In: Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.364>.

37. Wein, A., Bechara, M., Rohde, P.D., Vidal, M.-E.: Towards FAIR Data in Energy System Research: Challenges and Perspectives. Presented at the 4th Workshop on Metadata and Research (objects) Management for Linked Open Science June (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006474025>.
38. Stucky, K.-U., Koubaa, M.A., Liu, N., Schmidt, A., Süß, W., Hagenmeyer, V.: Towards a Conception and the Implementation of FAIR Data Management Tools for the Energy Domain. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10760965>.
39. Schwarz, J.S., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwert, C., Qussous, R., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., Weidlich, A., Hülk, L.: Developing an ontology for co-simulation scenarios of energy systems. Presented at the 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI) August 4 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736210>.
40. Schwarz, J.S., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwert, C., Qussous, R., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., Weidlich, A.: Towards an ontology for co-simulation scenarios of energy systems. Presented at the 2. NFDI4Energy Conference March 20 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15061653>.
41. Schmidt, A., Koubaa, M.A., Liu, N., Stucky, K.-U., Süß, W.: Metadata Extraction from a Huge Time Series Database. 1. NFDI4Energy Conference. (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10943975>.
42. Qussous, R., Schwarz, J.S., Pan, Z., Schmurr, P., Liu, N., Seiwert, C., Ferenz, S., German, R., Hagenmeyer, V., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A., Weidlich, A.: Refining Metadata for Energy Simulation Software. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736271>.
43. Pan, Z., Gao, Y., Ponci, F., Monti, A.: Semi-Automatic Ontology Development Framework for Building Energy Data Management. IEEE Access. 11, 111991–112003 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3323335>.
44. Muhammad, A., Engel, F.: An Ontology-Based Text Annotation Tool for NFDI4Energy. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735787>.
45. Muhammad, A., Engel, F.: Query Term Recommendation Using Domain-Specific Ontologies and Sentence Transformers. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988979>.
46. Ferenz, S., Werth, O., Nieße, A.: Requirements for a Metadata Scheme to Enable FAIR Energy Research Software. In: Electronic Communications of the EASST (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.14279/ECEASST.V83.2594>.
47. Ferenz, S., Nieße, A.: Towards Improved Findability of Energy Research Software by Introducing a Metadata-based Registry. ing.grid. 1, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48694/inggrid.3837>.

48. Wein, A., Engel, F., Hülk, L., Liu, N., Muhammad, A., Peters, F., Schmurr, P., Stappel, M., Steinert, A., Weko, S.: D4.1.1.1 Overview of Metadata and Ontology Interaction with NFDI4Energy Services. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18255229>.
49. Busse, C., Demandt, É., Deschler, K., Eberl, F., Eufinger, J., Fluck, J., Hennig, C., Jansen, L., Koepler, O., Krieger, U., Miller, B., Pempe, W., Schneide, C., Schrade, T., Schwarz, A., Seegert, J., Trippel, T., von Suchodoletz, D., Wiljes, C.: Leistungsfähige Entscheidungsstrukturen für ein NFDI-Dienstportfolio - Impulse zu Kriterien, Entscheidungsverfahren und Portfoliomanagement. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16356843>.
50. Kotthoff, F., Steinert, A., Werth, O., Ferez, S., Nieße, A.: D7.7.1.1 Designing a Consortium Service Portfolio – NFDI4Energy’s Criteria and Process for Integrating Services. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17700571>.
51. Karras, O., Göpfert, J., Kuckertz, P., Pelsler, T., Auer, S.: Organizing Scientific Knowledge From Energy System Research Using the Open Research Knowledge Graph. Presented at the 1. NFDI4Energy Conference February 20 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10560076>.
52. Rohde, P.D., Vidal, M.-E.: D4.4.2.3 1st Version of the Leibniz Data Manager. Zenodo (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652326>.
53. Rohde, P.D., Vidal, M.-E.: D4.4.1.1 Implementation of Federated Access. Zenodo (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652249>.
54. Rohde, P.D., Sakor, A., Brunet, M., Iglesias, E., Bechara, M., Arndt, S., Begoin, M., Kraft, A., Vidal, M.-E.: The Leibniz Data Manager: Supporting Researchers in the Lifecycle of Research Data. Presented at the 1. NFDI4Energy Conference March 4 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776314>.
55. Sedighi, F., Pan, Z., Gao, Y.: D3.3.1.1 List of required substitute data. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063698>.
56. Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J.S., Fuentes Grau, L., German, R., Lehnhoff, S., Monti, A., Nieße, A.: Towards a Simulation-as-a-Service Hub for the Energy Domain. 2. NFDI4Energy Conference. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15065996>.
57. Steinbrink, C., Blank-Babazadeh, M., El-Ama, A., Holly, S., Lüers, B., Nebel-Wenner, M., Ramírez Acosta, R.P., Raub, T., Schwarz, J.S., Stark, S., Nieße, A., Lehnhoff, S.: CPES Testing with mosaik: Co-Simulation Planning, Execution and Analysis. Appl. Sci. 9, 923 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9050923>.
58. Vogel, S., Eiling, N., Pitz, M., Bach, A., Stevic, M., Monti, P.A.: VILLASnode: An Open-Source Real-time Multi-protocol Gateway. J. Open Source Softw. 10, 8401 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.08401>.

59. Seiwerth, C., Halikulov, N., German, R.: D 5.3.3.1 Extending a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268434>.
60. Ferez, S., Jafarbigloo, A., Werth, O., Nieße, A.: SMECS: A Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software. In: Electronic Communications of the EASST (2025). <https://doi.org/10.14279/eceasst.v85.2708>.
61. Thiery, F., Flemisch, B., Bernoth, J., Seiwerth, C., Linxweiler, J., Söhn, L.: How to improve the visibility and added value of RSE(s) in NFDI. deRSE 2025. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14976366>.
62. Steinert, A., Brandt, T.: Using TimescaleDB and Apache Superset to support Co-Simulation Data Exploration. deRSE24 - Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany (deRSE24). (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725691>.
63. Seiwerth, C., Steinert, A., Fuentes Grau, L., Schwarz, J.S., Liu, N., Schmurr, P., Qussous, R., Pan, Z., Ferez, S., German, R.: From Start to Finish- The Ideal Process of Using Simulation Software in Energy Research Projects. deRSE 2025. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17710286>.
64. Seiwerth, C., Niebisch, M., Ferez, S., German, R.: Research Software Engineering in the Energy Domain as Part of NFDI4Energy. deRSE24 - Conference for Research Software Engineering in Germany (deRSE24). (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17710540>.
65. Ferez, S., Nieße, A.: Towards Services to Enable FAIR Research Software in a Typical Research Project Cycle. deRSE 2025. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968144>.
66. Ferez, S., Jafarbigloo, A., Werth, O., Nieße, A.: SMECS: A Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software. deRSE 2025. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968049>.
67. Ferez, S., Frost, E., Schrage, R., Wolgast, T., Werth, O., Nieße, A.: Towards Guidelines for Engineering of Energy Research Software. deRSE 2025. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968117>.
68. Hammitzsch, M., Busse, C., Flemisch, B., Förstner, K., Kalman, T., Löffler, F., Politze, M., Riehle, D.: Concept for Setting up a Working Group Research Software Engineering in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructures. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6483449>.
69. Seiwerth, C., Ferez, S.: Building a RSE Community in Energy Research. 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100689>.
70. Seiwerth, C., Schwarz, J.S., Fuentes Grau, L., Liu, N., Pan, Z., Qussous, R., Schmurr, P.: D5.4.6 A SMP Catalog for the Energy Research Software Engineering Community. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18254298>.
71. Speck, C., Schulz, T., Weinhardt, C.: D2.5.1.2 Mapping Energy Data Gaps and Reuse Barriers: Evidence and Implications for NFDI4Energy. Zenodo (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231310>.

72. Sedighi, F., Pan, Z., Monti, A.: Analysis of Data Substitution Requirements and Techniques in Energy Research. Presented at the 1. NFDI4Energy Conference April 23 (2024).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11046006>.

3 List of Acronyms

Table 3 List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CEPO	Climate and Energy Policy Ontology
CoRDI	Conference on Research Data Infrastructure
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EFZN	Energieforschungszentrum Niedersachsen (Energy Research Centre of the federal state of Lower Saxony)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERDM	Energy Research Data Management
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
HMC	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration
IAB	Industry Advisory Board
ID	Identifier
KgS	Konsortium gemäß Satzung (consortium in the association)
LDM	Leibniz Data Manager
NFDI	National Research Data Infrastructure
OEMetadata	Open Energy Metadata
OEO	Open Energy Ontology
ORKG	Open Research Knowledge Graph
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMO	Research Data Management Organizer
RSE	Research Software Engineering
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SIGEnergy	Special Interest Group Energy
SMECS	Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software